

Development, Assessment and Use of Geostatistical and Land Use Regression Models to Identify Areas with High Likelihood of Private Well Contamination

Development of National Screening and Site-specific Landscape Regression Models to Identify Areas with High Likelihood of Private Well Contamination

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List of Acronyms

AUC	Area under the receiver -operator curve
As	Arsenic
CART	Classification and Regression Tree models
CDC	Center for Disease Control and Prevention
Cl	Chloride
CWS	Community Water System
DAP	Dasymmetrically Apportioned Population Model
DEM	National Digital Elevation Model
Fe	Iron
HLR	Hydrologic Landscape Regions
IDW	Inverse Distant Weighting
KRIG	Ordinary Kriging
LR	Likelihood Ratio
LUR	Land Use Regression
MCL	Minimum Contaminant Level
MLRAs	Major Land Resource Areas
MN	Manganese
NLCD	National Land Cover Database
NO3	Nitrate
NO3-N	Nitrate as Nitrogen
NPV	Negative Predictive Value
NTN	National Atmospheric Deposition Program, National Trends Network
NURE	National Uranium Resource Evaluation
NWIS	USGS National Water Information System
PET	Potential evapotranspiration
PMPE	Precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration
PO4	Phosphate
ppb	Parts Per Billion
ppm	Parts Per Million
PPV	Positive Predictive Value
PRISM	Parameter-elevation Relationships on Independent Slopes Model
PWUA	Private Well Use Area
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SAGE	University of Wisconsin Center for Sustainability and the Global Environment
SO4	Sulfate
SSURGO	Soil Survey Geographic Database
STATSGO	State Soil Geographic Database
U	Uranium
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
USGS	United States Geological Survey
UWSP	University of Wisconsin Stevens Point

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Executive Summary

Approximately 45 million individuals rely on private wells or small systems not regulated by the Safe Drinking Water Act for their domestic drinking water supply. With the exception of a few states (e.g., WA and NJ), private wells or systems serving fewer than 15 connections are not required to regularly monitor water quality. This is a public health concern as a lack of information can lead to prolonged exposure to levels of contaminants that pose health risks. Without even basic information about groundwater quality or areas subject to elevated levels of contaminants of concern, effective public actions are limited.

To address this need, the Health Studies Branch of the National Center for Environmental Health, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) executed a contract with the Division of Public Health at the University of Utah to address these needs (Contract # 200-2013-57313). The overall goal of this project is *to develop, evaluate and apply methods to identify areas in the 48 contiguous states where contaminant levels in groundwater are likely to be elevated and may pose risks of adverse health effects, and to make these results easily accessible to environmental health practitioners.*

We evaluated four methods for predicting areas where groundwater concentrations of arsenic, uranium, or nitrate were elevated: land use regression (LUR), Classification and Regression Trees (CART), Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW), and Ordinary Kriging (KRIG). Three study sites were used for each contaminant. Study sites were based on USGS Physiographic Regions. The accuracy of the prediction method was evaluated using two-thirds of the sample to construct the predictive model, and the other third as a validation dataset. Cut-points used to define 'elevated' and normal samples were selected to maximize sensitivity subject to a minimum specificity of 0.70. Sensitivity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and the area under the receiver-operator curve (AUC) were used to compare the methods. The methods were also assessed in terms of the software, data, and skills needed to implement the method.

Of the 36 case studies (three contaminants x three study sites x four methods), there were few differences in the predictive ability across the four methods and the three contaminants. AUC values ranged from 0.73 to 0.90 with an overall mean of 0.83 (good); 31 of the 36 case studies had AUC values above 0.80. Model performance did vary for any given method between sites and between contaminants (max difference between sites or within contaminants = 0.10). Average sensitivity when the specificity was above 0.70 was 80.6%. Average sensitivity for models predicting arsenic (86.3%) was somewhat better than for uranium (78.4%) or nitrate (77.1%). PPVs were modest (average=30.4%),

reflecting the substantial number of wells that were misclassified as 'elevated.' Still, wells classified as 'elevated' were over three times as likely to be elevated as not.

The accuracy of any of the four methods evaluated in this report is limited by the spatial coverage of wells with groundwater quality data as well as the availability of site specific characteristics and geochemical data. The two geostatistical interpolation methods, IDW and ordinary kriging, have the advantage of needing only good location information and the concentration of the target contaminant(s). Both interpolation methods can be carried out using routines in ArcGIS with an advanced GIS user. However, the spatial pattern of concentration levels, e.g., wells with high contaminant levels surrounded by wells with low contaminant levels, can result in smoothing that underestimates the contaminant level. This problem occurs more frequently with ordinary kriging than IDW. With geochemical data, LUR can be used to predict concentrations for wells that have chemical data but are lacking data for the target contaminants. This increases the number of wells/locations where predicted values can be generated. However, these predictions are still just for points and interpolation, such as IDW, needs to be used to generate predictions for other locations. While predictions for nitrate can be made for any location based on site characteristics, site specific information for these locations must be compiled. We have compiled such information for the contiguous US. LUR also requires statistical software and someone with experience creating statistical models. CART has the advantage of creating models that are flexible in the effects that factors can have on predictions and it intuitively makes sense. However, the software is difficult to use and requires a person with at least intermediate statistical skills. Overall, IDW is the easiest to implement and we recommend IDW for practitioners who wish to improve on the National Private Well Water Screening maps we have created

1 Introduction

1.1 Problem statement

Approximately 45 million individuals rely on private wells or small systems not regulated by the Safe Drinking Water Act for their domestic drinking water supply (Kenny et al., 2009). With the exception of a few states (e.g., WA and NJ), private wells or systems serving fewer than 15 connections are not required to regularly monitor water quality (Vanderslice, 2011). This is a public health concern as a lack of information can lead to prolonged exposure to contaminant levels that pose health risks. Private wells are more susceptible to contamination as they are shallow (<100 ft.) and are often located in agricultural areas (Nolan & Hitt, 2006). Based on USGS data, arsenic, nitrate/nitrite, and uranium-238 exceeded their respective MCLs in 11%, 8%, and 4% of the wells tested, respectively, and nitrate levels have increased (Focazio et al., 2006; DeSimone et al., 2009; Bartholomay et al., 2007).

While elevated concentrations of contaminants in private wells pose serious concerns, it is difficult for public health agencies to effectively identify problem areas as most local environmental health programs are self-funded (e.g., food safety inspections) and few health departments have dedicated funds to pay for staff or testing. Without basic information about groundwater quality or areas subject to elevated levels of contaminants of concern, effective public actions are limited.

To address this need, the Health Studies Branch of the National Center for Environmental Health, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) executed a contract with the Division of Public Health at the University of Utah to address these needs (Contract # 200-2013-57313).

1.2 Objectives

The overall goal of this project is *to develop, evaluate and apply methods to identify areas in the 48 contiguous states where contaminant levels in groundwater are likely to be elevated and may pose risks of adverse health effects, and to make these results easily accessible to environmental health practitioners*. This project has three objectives:

Phase I: National Screening Model. Develop, evaluate and implement a nationwide well water quality screening model/algorithm that classifies geographic regions (where private wells are likely being used) according to the potential for having elevated concentrations of contaminants in private wells, and characterize the level of uncertainty associated with the classification.

Phase II: Landscape Regression and Geostatistical Predictive Models. Develop and evaluate landscape regression and geostatistical models designed to identify specific areas with elevated concentrations of contaminants of concern.

Phase III: Dissemination of Results and Methods. Disseminate methods and results to the public health practice community and provide guidance and underlying data to facilitate use by local and state practitioners.

1.3 Phase II Specific Tasks

The specific tasks specified for Phase II were:

1. Identify sites for case studies
2. Identify and compile site-specific data on explanatory factors
3. Compile, integrate and interpret site-specific geologic data (As and U)
4. Identify and compile site specific groundwater quality data
5. Develop geostatistical models
6. Develop and evaluate landscape regression models
7. Produce report, guidance document and data products

The work completed to address these tasks is presented in this document. This document is organized into five sections. Following this introduction is a section describing the overall methodology. The development and evaluation of the models are presented for each of the three contaminants of concern: arsenic, uranium, and nitrate. The final section provides guidance to potential users regarding the methods to generate predictive models for their specific geographic region, and recommendations for further model development and application.

2 Methodology

2.1 Approach

Our general approach was to develop predictive models for each contaminant (e.g., arsenic, uranium, and nitrate) at three contaminant-specific sites using four modeling techniques: Land Use Regression (LUR), Classification and Regression Tree models (CART), Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW), and Ordinary Kriging (KRIG). LUR and CART used a dichotomous outcome indicating whether the concentration was above or below a specified threshold. The resulting models were not constrained to have the same variables across sites. Predicted values were generated from each model for the entire dataset. A dichotomous variable indicating whether the predicted value was above or below the same threshold was created from the predicted values. IDW and KRIG predicted the concentration of each contaminant across the study sites. These geostatistical models were developed independently using a randomly chosen subset of the available data.

All models were estimated using a randomly-selected sample of approximately two-thirds of the available data. The other third of the dataset was used for validation and was not used to generate the models. The methods were evaluated by comparing the predicted level of the target contaminant (above or below the threshold) to the actual level (above or below the same threshold) for the validation dataset.

2.2 Study Sites

2.2.1 *Selection of Study Sites*

Models for each contaminant were developed for three contaminant-specific study sites. Study sites were based on the USGS Physiographic Regions (<http://tapestry.usgs.gov/physiogr/physio.html>). These regions were developed by Nevin Fenneman based on terrain texture, rock type, geologic history and structure (Fenneman & Johnson, 1946). This provides a basis for selecting areas that are likely to be more similar in the conditions governing the concentrations of the three target contaminants than the use of political boundaries.

Single physiographic sections, provinces, or aggregations of sections were used to define study sites. Sites were chosen to represent a variety of conditions for areas where there were known elevations of the target contaminant. Wisconsin was chosen as the sixth study site because we were able to access a large groundwater database covering the state. The physiographic regions assigned to each study site are presented in Table 1, and detailed descriptions are presented below. Populations

were acquired from the private well use areas (PWUAs) for each study site (U.S. Census 2010 populations). The hydrologic basins were acquired from The United States Department of Agriculture’s Watershed Boundary Datasets (USDA). The remaining statistics were derived from a spatial query of the USGS’s hydrologic landscape regions of the United States (Wolock, 2004).

Table 1. Study sites used for each target contaminant.

Site	Physiographic regions	As	U	NO3
1	20c,d	X		
2	3a			X
3	12f	X	X	
4	13d,f		X	X
5	24e		X	
6	WI	X		X

2.3 Model Specification

2.3.1 *Arsenic*

We considered geologic formation, groundwater geochemistry, and hydrometeorological factors to be the primary factors influencing the concentration of arsenic in groundwater. The rationale for using these factors and the results of preliminary analyses that guided our model development are presented in this section.

Geologic formation and specific aquifer. The concentration of arsenic and other minerals in geologic formations can influence the resulting concentration of arsenic in groundwater. Geologic formation spatial data were retrieved from the USGS and several state sources (see Appendix A). While these data included formation names, there was limited information on mineral content. Some datasets distinguished between surficial and underlying formations, however the depths of the formations were not available. The USGS’s National Water Information System (NWIS) groundwater data also contained attribute information about the geologic layers and associated aquifers in an unstructured text field. However, there were many name variations for the same formation and the sample aquifer was not consistent, even for multiple samples from the same well or proximate wells with the same depth. Further, about 30% of the formations listed were ‘Unconsolidated,’ which did not give any indication of the parent material. When linkages between a well’s aquifer formation and the formation from our

spatial datasets were possible, wells often fell outside of the formation boundary (Figure 1). Because of these limitations we did not use geologic formation or aquifer type in the predictive models.

Figure 1. Wells from a test area (Tennessee and Georgia) were displayed by their principle aquifer and colored with the same coloring scheme as the underlying principal aquifers. Although many wells corresponded to their underlying designated principal aquifers, there were many occurrences (especially near borders) of mismatches between wells (as designated in the NWIS database) and the underlying principal aquifer (e.g., circled area). Because the mismatches could not be reconciled by considering stratigraphic relationships (possible correspondence of principal aquifer at greater depth), organization by principal aquifer was not considered useful. Furthermore, high concentration As wells appeared to be clustered by much smaller spatial units than principal aquifer extents.

Evaporative concentration. A primary governor of certain trace element concentrations in water (e.g., arsenic and selenium) is the hydrometeorological setting. These trace element concentrations tend to be enhanced in environments that promote the concentration of elements in water, i.e., arid environments. The primary factors that indicate such conditions are precipitation and evapotranspiration, bogs/presence of standing water, frequent flooding, proximity to surface waters, slope as an indicator of runoff rate, and soil permeability.

Sorption and dissolution. Arsenic (As) occurs in multiple forms (species) depending on the geocontaminant environment, i.e. the electron activity and pH. Arsenic undergoes redox transformation in response to the geocontaminant environments set by the prevalence of organic matter and electron acceptors. Arsenic in oxic waters (oxygen rich) occurs in dissolved form: arsenate (AsO_4^{3-} , +V oxidation state). In reduced settings (oxygen poor) lacking sulfide, arsenic occurs as arsenite (AsO_3^{3-} , +III oxidation state). In sulfide-rich reduced settings, it occurs in immobile sulfide mineral forms such as orpiment (As_2S_3). These changes in As speciation are shown in Figure 2 using solid lines to denote boundaries of prevalent species. Notably, at pH below ~ 7.5 , arsenate (and to a lesser extent arsenite) is immobilized by strong sorption of these negatively-charged oxyanions to ubiquitous positively charged iron oxyhydroxides that occur in oxic sediment. Changes in iron speciation with pe and pH (e.g., iron oxyhydroxide stability) are shown in Figure 2 using dashed lines to denote boundaries of prevalent species. The solid form of iron (iron oxyhydroxides) occur in the stability fields corresponding to Fe^{3+} and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$. The dissolved form of iron occurs in the stability fields corresponding to Fe^{2+} and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$.

Figure 2. A pe vs pH diagram for arsenic (solid lines) is overlain by a pe vs pH diagram for iron (dashed lines). The boundary between Mn^{4+} and Mn^{2+} is shown (dotted line). The blue shading represents

geocontaminant conditions where arsenic is expected to be immobile, and the yellow shading represents geocontaminant conditions where arsenic is expected to be mobile. Angled stripes indicate mobility in the presence of elevated phosphate (>0.5 ppm). Vertical stripes indicate mobility in the presence of either elevated phosphate or elevated sulfate (>10 ppm). The region labeled 1, represents the stable field for Mn oxyhydroxides, which immobilize H_3AsO_3^0 . The white region represents an area of uncertainty with respect to arsenic mobility. The boundaries for each species was determined in Geochemist's Workbench assuming concentrations of 10 ppb arsenic, 100 ppm iron, 10 ppm sulfate, and 50 ppm manganese.

With this information as a platform it is possible to predict the geocontaminant environments in which arsenic can be expected to be relatively mobile, and therefore potentially elevated in groundwater. The following description is derived from Stollenwerk, 2003, Ayotte et al., 2003, and Anning et al., 2012. Ostensibly, oxyanions of arsenic are mobile under oxidizing conditions (high pe) and immobile under highly reducing (sulfate reducing) conditions, where they are complexed in sulfide minerals. However, oxyanions (e.g., As(V)) are immobilized by ubiquitous iron-oxyhydroxides in oxic settings. The +V oxyanions (H_3AsO_4 and H_2AsO_4^-) sorb to the positively charged iron oxyhydroxides, rendering arsenic immobile below pH 6.9 (Figure 2). Phosphate displaces (as a competing counter ion) arsenic oxyanions from iron oxyhydroxides, rendering arsenic mobile. At elevated pH the surface of the iron oxyhydroxides becomes negative, thereby reducing oxyanion sorption, rendering arsenic mobile (Figure 2). Under iron reducing conditions, which are a function of both pe and pH as shown by the yellow region in Figure 2, iron oxyhydroxides dissolve, thereby mobilizing arsenic. Furthermore, under these conditions As(V) is reduced to As(III) which sorbs less than As(V) to iron oxyhydroxides, further contributing to arsenic mobilization (Figure 2). In the field labeled "1", Mn-oxyhydroxides remain stable, and H_3AsO_3^0 is immobilized via inner-sphere complexation with -OH groups on the Mn oxyhydroxide surface. This is true except when sulfate is present, as it out competes As(III) for the Mn oxyhydroxide surface (Stollenwerk, 2003) (Figure 2). In the field labeled "2", Fe oxyhydroxides remain stable, and neutral As(III) (H_3AsO_3^0) is immobilized via complexation with -OH groups on the Fe oxyhydroxide surface, except when phosphate is present (Figure 2) (Stollenwerk, 2003). At pH values above 9, As(III) forms oxyanions ($\text{H}_2\text{AsO}_3^{-1}$ and HAsO_3^{-2}) which do not bind to iron oxyhydroxides, mobilizing arsenic (Figure 2). At pe values less than 4, As(III) is bound in sulfide minerals. Therefore we expect pH, PO_4 , SO_4 and potentially NO_3 to be important predictors of arsenic concentrations.

2.3.2 Uranium

Like arsenic, uranium (U) also undergoes so-called redox transformation in response to the geocontaminant environments set by the prevalence of organic matter and the electron acceptors described above in Section 2.3.1. Uranium in oxic natural waters occurs in dissolved form: uranyl carbonate ($\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)$, +VI oxidation state). In reduced settings uranium occurs as an insoluble uranium oxide (UO_2 , +IV oxidation state). These changes in uranium speciation are shown in Figure 3 using solid lines to denote boundaries of prevalent species.

Figure 3. A pe vs pH diagram for uranium (solid lines) is overlain by a pe vs pH diagram for iron (dashed lines). The blue shading represents geocontaminant conditions where uranium is expected to be immobile and the yellow shading represents geocontaminant conditions where uranium is expected to be mobile. Angled stripes indicate mobility in the presence of elevated sulfate (>10 ppm). The boundaries for each species were determined in Geochemist's Workbench assuming concentrations of 30 ppb uranium, 100 ppm iron, and 10 ppm sulfate.

Notably, at pH below ~4, uranyl carbonate is immobilized by strong sorption of these negatively-charged oxyanions to ubiquitous positively charged iron oxyhydroxides that occur in oxic settings. Changes in iron speciation with pe and pH (e.g., iron oxyhydroxide stability) are shown in Figure 3 using dashed lines to denote boundaries of prevalent species. The solid form of iron (iron oxyhydroxides) occur in the stability fields corresponding to Fe^{3+} and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$. The dissolved form of iron occurs in the stability fields corresponding to Fe^{2+} and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$.

With this information as a platform it is possible to predict the geocontaminant environments in which uranium can be expected to be relatively mobile, and therefore potentially elevated in groundwater. The following description is derived from Zavodska et al., 2008; Bachmaf et al., 2008; and Hsi and Langmuir, 1985. Ostensibly, uranium is mobile under oxidizing conditions (high pe) and immobile under highly reducing (sulfate reducing) conditions, where it forms mineral complexes. However, oxyanions (e.g., U(VI)) are immobilized by ubiquitous iron-oxyhydroxides in oxic settings. The +VI oxyanion (UO_2^{2+}) sorbs to the positively charged iron oxyhydroxides, rendering uranium immobile below pH 3 (Figure 3). Sulfate displaces (as a competing counter ion) uranium oxyanions from iron oxyhydroxides, rendering uranium mobile. At pH greater than 4, uranyl ion is able to form stable, soluble, complexes with carbonate, thereby reducing oxyanion sorption, allowing uranium to remain mobile in solution (Figure 3). Under iron reducing conditions which are a function of both pe and pH as shown by the yellow region in Figure 3, iron oxyhydroxides dissolve, thereby mobilizing uranyl oxyanions. At pe values less than 5, U(VI) (the dominant species of uranium, present as U(IV) U_4O_9 and UO_2) is mineralized with phosphates, silicates, and arsenates and is rendered immobile.

Uranium is a radioactive element, which gives rise to most naturally occurring radioactivity in water through the decay into its daughter products. Uranium is commonly found in the presence of other radioactive constituents like Radium and Radon. Radon-222 (Rn-222) is a daughter product of both U-238 (a uranium isotope) and Ra-226 and is soluble in water. Radium-226 is present in country rock and is decayed and desorbed into an aquifer as Rn-222. Where Rn-222 is present in large quantities, there is a greater likelihood for elevated uranium. Therefore we expect oxidizing conditions, pH and SO_4 to be important predictors of the concentration of uranium.

2.3.3 Nitrate

Groundwater nitrate concentrations are a function of two factors: sources of nitrate and variables enhancing or inhibiting the movement of nitrate into the aquifer. Application of nitrogen based fertilizers is the primary source of nitrate in groundwater (Nolan, 2001; Nolan & Hitt, 2006; Nolan et al., 1997, 2002; Greene et al., 2004; Frans, 2008; Greene et al., 2004, 2005). Septic tank effluent is also high in nitrate and could be a significant source in areas of high population density and lack of sewerage (Del Rosario et al., 2014). Atmospheric deposition of nitrogen species may also contribute to nitrate in groundwater, but is likely a minor source (EPA, 2002).

Several site-specific factors increase or impede the transport of nitrogen through the soil column to the underlying aquifer. Heavy and/or consistent rainfall increases nitrate transport as nitrate is easily dissolved in water and does not tend to adsorb to soil particles. Irrigation or flooding will have a similar effect. High evapotranspiration will offset the effects of rainfall or irrigation. Proximate surface water can impact flow of groundwater but the effect depends on whether the aquifer is recharging the aquifer or is contributing to the water body.

Slope can affect the degree to which rainfall percolates into the soil or runs off into surface waters. Soil and bedrock can impact infiltration of rain water or irrigation water. Nitrate is more likely to be transported quickly into the underlying aquifer if the soil is permeable and if the aquifer is unconfined. Well depth is important as deeper wells are more likely to tap aquifers that lie under less permeable layer or impermeable layers. Nitrogen inputs, rainfall, irrigation, and soil type may have little to no effect on nitrate concentration in confined aquifers. Even in unconfined aquifers, greater depth will increase the time it takes for nitrate levels to increase as diffusion rather than advection becomes the primary process governing transport.

Given this understanding our models will consider the following factors: nitrogen inputs, hydrological factors affecting transport, and soil characteristics affecting flow.

2.4 Groundwater Quality Data

Data from NWIS and National Uranium Resource Evaluation (NURE) were used as the primary source of groundwater quality data for study sites 1 – 5. All NWIS groundwater data for the contiguous US were downloaded from the Water Quality Portal (<http://www.waterqualitydata.us/portal.jsp>). All available groundwater data held in NURE were also downloaded. Data from private wells in Wisconsin were provided by the Groundwater Center at the University of Wisconsin Stevens Point (UWSP). UWSP regularly tests water for citizens in Wisconsin and stores sample results. The UWSP collects and maintains a historical and ongoing database on private wells for the last twenty years. The database also includes data collected by the Wisconsin Department of Agriculture Trade and Consumer Protection and the Wisconsin Department of Natural Resources.

Data for over 35 constituents were included in the data retrieval process. Data were processed to combine equivalent data having unique parameter codes. Units were standardized when needed. All data were screened and unrealistic values were removed. Values that were noted as being below detection or reporting limits were replaced by one-half the censoring value (e.g., level of detection, reporting limit, practical quantitation limit), and all censored values were flagged. When a censoring value was not reported for a specific measured concentration, the median of reported censoring values was used. There were too few observations from individual wells to employ other imputation techniques. When more than one observation was made in a day, or when there were data for equivalent measures on the same day, the mean value was used.

Many of the wells retrieved from NWIS and NURE were reported to be < 50 feet deep, and these wells had much higher levels of nitrate. The available data did not include information about the use of the well (e.g., domestic, livestock, research). Wells for domestic use are typically recommended to be at least 50 feet deep to the screened portion. Domestic well less than 50 feet are at much greater risk of contamination and may pose risks regardless of the site characteristics. As such, only the data from wells with a reported depth of 50 to 600 feet were used to better represent conditions in most private domestic wells. Well depth was not available for the Wisconsin data.

NWIS includes data collected from early in the 20th century, while the NURE sampling program occurred from 1975 to 1980. Arsenic and uranium observations from samples taken since 1970 were considered to be sufficiently reliable and were used for all analyses. Only nitrate samples collected in 1999 or later were used in the nitrate analyses. The numbers of observations and summary statistics for

each site are presented in their respective sections. SAS (ver. 9.4) and STATA (ver. 13) were used to process the data.

NWIS and NURE data include geographic coordinates, and NURE data are available as a geo-database. The Wisconsin data only had approximate well locations, typically the centroid of the relevant quarter-quarter section. All observations were geo-located and were projected into UTM coordinates (NAD 83) using ArcGIS (ver. 10.2).

2.5 Groundwater Quality Determinant Data

Many types of data that could be potentially useful for explaining and predicting groundwater As, U, or NO₃ levels were compiled. While most of these datasets were to be compiled for only the study sites, we expanded the scope of the project by compiling and processing all data for the contiguous US, and then used this full set of data to improve our National Screening Model. A brief description of each data source is provided in Appendix A.

2.5.1 Groundwater geochemistry data

Arsenic and uranium concentrations are affected by the geochemistry of the groundwater. Comprehensive groundwater geochemistry data were available from, NWIS, NURE and the Wisconsin databases. These datasets included data on pH, alkalinity, PO₄, SO₄, Mn, Cl⁻, specific conductance, and other inorganic constituents.

2.5.2 Geologic formations and principle aquifers

The presence of arsenic and uranium varies by geologic formation. Geologic formation data were obtained from the USGS and multiple state sources. A comprehensive list of available state data was compiled into an Excel spreadsheet. Concentrations of As and/or U may be similar within a specific aquifer. Principal aquifer spatial data, obtained from the USGS, were used to link water quality data to their aquifer. NWIS data also had fields identifying the formation and aquifer associated with the well. These data were not standardized or consistent and did not correspond well to the geologic formation or principal aquifer.

2.5.3 Oxidic/anoxic conditions

The oxidic state can affect the dissolution and binding of As and U. Precipitation, potential evapotranspiration (PET), and precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration (PMPE) were estimated

for each sub-watershed (or Hydrologic Landscape Region (HLR); n=39,833) and were used as proxies for the level of oxygenation, as was the frequency of ponding (SSURGO soil survey).

2.5.4 *Sources of nitrogen*

Agricultural fertilizers. Nitrogen from agricultural fertilizers is a significant source of nitrate in groundwater. Nitrogen application rates around each well were estimated using crop-specific recommended application rates, and satellite derived spatial data of crop patterns (<http://nassgeodata.gmu.edu/CropScape/>). Cropscape raster images have a resolution of 30m and each pixel indicates the land use in terms of 105 specific crops and 21 non-agricultural land use types. Crops were categorized based on nitrogen fertilizer needs (high-, medium-, and low-N fertilizer use) and crop type (see Appendix A). Crop type categories included grains and seeds (high-, med-, and low-N use), stone/miscellaneous fruits (high-, med-, and low-N use), other fruit-berries (low-N use), nuts (high-N use), legumes (med- and low-N use), truck crops (high- and medium-N use), and pasture (high-N use). These 13 agricultural and 5 non-agricultural categories were then used to reclassify each state's Cropscape raster layer.

To determine the type and area of crops around a well, 500 m buffers were constructed around each well and the proportion of the buffer area associated with each nitrogen application category was calculated. Cropscape data for 2008, 2010, and 2012 were used to generate nitrogen application rates for water samples taken between 2007 and 2013. For samples taken between 1999 and 2006, National Land Cover Datasets (NLCD 2001 and 2006) were used to estimate the proportion of the well buffer covered by pasture/hay and cultivated crops (<http://www.mrlc.gov/>). Annual county-level estimates of annual farm and non-farm fertilizer usage from the USDA Census of Agriculture were also used.

Septic tank effluent. Population was used as a proxy for nitrogen loading from septic tanks. The population was calculated as the total population in PWUAs whose centroids were within 500 m of the well. PWUAs are generally the same size or smaller than Census blocks. Population counts were derived from US Census 2000 and 2010 data. The proportion of the 500 m well buffer that is urbanized was generated from US Census designation of urbanized areas and urban clusters.

Atmospheric nitrogen deposition. Atmospheric deposition of nitrogen was based on models from the National Atmospheric Deposition Program (<http://nadp.sws.uiuc.edu/>). Mean deposition levels were calculated for the 500 m buffer around each well using yearly data corresponding to the sample year.

2.5.5 *Factors affecting nitrogen transport: rainfall and irrigation*

Rainfall. Monthly and annual precipitation for each well was based on PRISM datasets (<http://www.prism.oregonstate.edu/>). Annual rainfall totals were extracted for each well location and monthly rainfall was estimated as the annual total adjusted by the proportion of annual rainfall occurring in each month over the past 30 years. This was also calculated with a one month lag. Average rainfall was also available for each HLR.

Irrigation. An estimate of the proportion of area within 500 m that was irrigated was calculated using the University of Wisconsin raster dataset derived from remote sensing (see Appendix A). Each 500 m² pixel is characterized by the percent of area that is irrigated. The overall irrigated proportion of the 500 m well buffer was calculated based on the proportion of the pixel in the buffer and the percent irrigated. For time periods before 2001, irrigation datasets were binary and each pixel was classified as irrigated or not. In this case, the total number of positive pixels in the buffer was used to calculate irrigated area.

Surface waters. Proximate surface water can increase inflow into underlying aquifers. The USGS national hydrography layer (<http://nhd.usgs.gov>) contains information on surface water for the US and is at the 1:24k-scale. The percentage of water area, as well as the type of water body (e.g., permanent lakes, intermittent lakes, and permanent streams or rivers), was calculated for all 500 m well buffers.

2.5.6 *Factors affecting nitrogen transport: Soil and surface conditions*

Slope. Slope can affect the rate of overland flow and run-off during a rainfall event. Several measures of slope were generated. Average slope within the 500 m well buffer was calculated based on the National Digital Elevation Model (<http://ned.usgs.gov/>). Slope at the site was also derived for the buffer area using soil survey data (SSURGO). The HLR also provides slope for each HLR as well as for the upland and lowland parts of the HLR separately.

Impervious surface. The NLCD Impervious surface data (<http://www.mrlc.gov>) was used to determine the proportion of impervious area within each 500 m well buffer. The average of the estimated proportion of each 30 m² raster cell within the buffer was used as the measure of impervious surface.

Soil drainage. Detailed soil information is available from the USDA's SSURGO and STATSGO soil surveys. Soil data is organized into map units with SSURGO being the most detailed. The map units within each 500 m well buffer was compiled to compute the percentage of land in that buffer where the

soil was graded as having high (group A) or moderate (group B) infiltration rates. Similarly, we calculated the percentage of the buffer where the soils were ‘well drained’ or ‘excessively well-drained’ as well as the percentage of the soil that was sand and whether the area had regular ponding. These soil indicators represented the conditions in the top two meters of the soil.

2.5.7 Spatial Processing

Three techniques were used to generate data representing characteristics at or around each well. For spatial data with a high degree of variability on a small scale, whether raster or vector format, the attribute was summed or average with a 500 m buffer around each well using the zonal statistics tool (raster data) or the tabulate intersect tool (vector data) from ArcMap 10.2. The value of the layer at the well point was used for attributes that were constant over a large area (e.g., county fertilizer use).

2.6 Predictive Modeling Methods

Four types of prediction models were implemented and assessed. These methods were selected because they have been used in previous work and they are more easily translated to audiences who do not have advanced statistical training. One of our goals was to develop models that ‘made sense,’ that is, where the relationships between the predictors and the outcome were plausible. Such models would be more likely to be understood and seen as credible by practitioners and the public, and thus, more apt to be used for action. Further, models that are congruent with known relationships between determinants and outcome concentrations may be more generalizable to other situations.

2.6.1 Land Use Regression (LUR) models

Land use or landscape regression models of groundwater quality attempt to relate the concentration, or probability of exceeding a threshold concentration, as a function of characteristics at or near the well. In our context, we consider the geocontaminant characteristics of the groundwater at the well as one of the characteristics of that site. Such groundwater geocontaminant data is theoretically and empirically linked to concentrations of arsenic, uranium, and nitrate. Further, there are many situations where groundwater samples have been analyzed for some common geocontaminant parameters, such as pH and specific conductance, but not for more difficult to measure parameters such as arsenic or uranium.

We used unconditional logistic regression to estimate odds ratios describing the association between each of the explanatory variables and an indicator variable signaling that the observed concentration was greater than the threshold value. A forward selection procedure was used to identify

variables which were significant at the $p \leq 0.20$ level. Starting with this group, variables were added and dropped to obtain a model with plausible relationships. Both continuous variables and categorical variables derived from the continuous variables were considered. Models stratified by $\text{pH} >$ or ≤ 7.5 were also estimated, but the results were not appreciably different from the full model. As the ultimate goal of this process was prediction, the model was further adjusted to increase the explanatory power of the model, as measured by the “Pseudo $-r^2$ ” statistic. Generally, the variable needed to have a p-value ≤ 0.20 to remain in the model. However, there were circumstances where including a variable with a higher p-value was allowed as it appeared to correct for confounding and produced much more realistic parameter estimates based on expert opinion. The final models represented a balance of explanatory power and plausibility without including all possible factors regardless of the strength or direction of the association. All analyses were carried out using STATA ver. 13 (College Park, Texas).

These models were estimated using a randomly-selected sample of approximately two-thirds of the available data. The other third of the dataset was used for the validation. Once the final model had been estimated, predicted probabilities of exceedance were generated as a function of the explanatory variables using all available observations. The model evaluation procedure is described in Section 2.7 below.

We recognize that this procedure may not lead other researchers to the same final models. However, it is the process that would likely be used by practitioners. We further recognize that this approach would not be appropriate when estimating the relationship between variables as only those relationships that fit previous hypotheses may be selected.

2.6.2 *Classification and Regression Trees (CART) models*

Classification and Regression Trees is a collection of estimation methods used primarily for data mining and prediction. Classification trees are used because they allow for very flexible hierarchical models that effectively include different interactions for each level of a previous predictor. Typically the user will set model parameters (e.g., maximum number of branches or leaves, minimum sample size in a leaf) and the algorithm will find the classification scheme that produces the most distinct groupings, as measured by a chi-square statistic. While the algorithm will produce the best fit model for prediction based on the given data, often the results are uninterpretable. For example, the algorithm would split the observations into groups based on the level of rainfall. While the split would produce the most distinct groups, the proportion of observations above a threshold concentration may jump from high to

low and back to high across widely variables ranges of rainfall. Such splits do not demonstrate any consistent pattern and would not 'make sense' to a practical user.

As with the LUR modeling, we used a supervised model building procedure, informed by expert opinion, theory, and previous empirical observations regarding the relationships between the explanatory variables and the observed concentrations of the target contaminants. The same binary variables indicating that the concentration of the contaminant was above a set threshold used for the LUR models were also used for the CART analyses. The top-level factor was selected such that there was good discrimination and a plausible, consistent trend in the proportion positive observed across the groupings. Observations where the explanatory variable was a missing value were always kept in a separate group (branch). Where more than one factor could be used for the top level, alternative models were generated to see which model produced plausible second-level groupings.

Generally we did not allow for more than five groupings (branches) per variable or four levels per model. A minimum sample size of 25 for each group (leaf) was maintained, with a preferred target of 100. Analyses were carried out using SAS Enterprise Miner Workstation (ver. 12.3). The SAS code for generating the expected frequencies of positive results (e.g., exceedance of the threshold value) based on the explanatory variables was exported from the software and used in a SAS program to generate expected frequencies, which we interpreted as predicted probabilities of exceedance. At each study site, the same randomly-selected observations were used for model estimation in all four analyses, and the remaining observations were used for model evaluation. Predicted probabilities were generated for all observations using the scoring algorithm based on the final CART model.

2.6.3 *Geostatistical interpolation methods*

Interpolation algorithms use known values from a set a sample points to estimate unknown values over a larger area (Bailey & Gatrell, 1995). Interpolation algorithms are commonly used to generate estimates of spatially continuous phenomena, such as rainfall, temperature, air pressure, soil salinity, and pollutant concentrations in air, water, or on land. The general objectives of interpolation are: (1) to model an attribute's pattern over a larger area, (2) to identify potential variables that are related to the attribute, and (3) to predict values in areas where observations are lacking (Bailey & Gatrell, 1995). Inverse distance weighting (IDW) and ordinary kriging were used separately to estimate arsenic, uranium, and nitrate concentrations between study site wells where contaminant observations were available.

IDW creates a value for every point on a grid with the value at unsampled locations being an average of surrounding observations. Observations are weighted by the inverse square of the distance from the observed value to the point being predicted, so that nearby observations have a stronger influence on the predicted level than observations further away. The power parameter determines the influence of distance on neighborhood weights. If the power is 0 then the value at the predicted location will be the mean of all neighborhood observations regardless of distance. As the power value increases, the weights of observations further away from the predicted location diminish (Bailey & Gatrell, 1995). Neighborhoods can be defined by the number of neighbors, a circular neighborhood distance, a circular neighborhood distance split into sectors, or by a combination of distance and neighbors.

Kriging is a geostatistical algorithm that interpolates a surface from observations taken at a set of known point locations to improve the estimation and prediction of the mean surface through the incorporation of the local covariance structure (Hengl, 2007; Bailey & Gatrell, 1995). Kriging examines the distance and direction of every set of points to quantify the spatial autocorrelation of the sample dataset. Covariograms, variograms, and correlograms are used to examine the spatial dependence or interaction of the spatially continuous process, e.g., how values at different locations are related to each other. Based on a best-fit model, unknown values are predicted over the whole study area. Two general and widely used types of kriging are ordinary and universal kriging, both of which can be implemented in ESRI's ArcGIS. Ordinary kriging assumes that the global trend is constant, but unknown, i.e., it assumes that the first-order effect is stationary. Universal kriging assumes that the global trend varies throughout a study region and its structure is unknown, i.e., it assumes that the first-order effect is non-stationary (Bailey & Gatrell, 1995). The covariance structure for both ordinary and universal kriging is estimated from the covariogram and variogram of the observed data.

IDW was implemented using ESRI's ArcGIS 10.2 Geostatistical Analyst (GA). Model parameters include power, neighborhood type, max/min neighbors, sector type, and major/minor semiaxes (Table 2). For the majority of study sites, a standard neighborhood type with four sectors was used with the maximum and minimum neighbors being 15 and 10, respectively. Nearest neighbor calculations were made for each study site, which provided the average nearest neighbor (NN) distance among all wells in the training datasets. The starting point for determining the neighborhood size was informed by the average NN distance for each study site, however the neighborhoods were often 1.5 times larger than

the average NN distance. The power parameter determines the influence of distance on neighborhood weights and was optimized to minimize the root mean square error (RMSE).

Table 2. IDW parameters for contaminant study sites.

Study Sites	Power	Neighborhood Type	Max Neighbors	Min Neighbors	Sectors	Major/Minor Semiaxes (m)	Average NN Distance(m)
Arsenic							
1	1.23	Standard	15	10	4	4000	2650
3	1.00	Standard	15	10	4	5000	3385
6	1.93	Standard	5	2	4	750	783
Uranium							
3	1.34	Standard	15	10	4	5500	3648
4	1.12	Standard	15	10	4	6500	4441
5	1.00	Standard	15	10	4	4500	3133
Nitrate							
2	1.00	Standard	15	10	4	2500	1574
4	1.44	Standard	15	10	4	6000	4069
6	1.25	Standard	15	10	4	1000	450

Ordinary kriging was implemented using ESRI’s ArcGIS 10.2 Geostatistical Analyst. Either a semivariogram or covariance function was fitted to each study site’s training dataset using a stable model. Additional model parameters included the major range, lag size, number of lags, neighborhood type, max/min neighbors, and sector type (Table 3). Major range represents a distance beyond which there is little or no correlation. Major range values were largely determined by the “optimization” option within the GA, which focuses on the estimation of the range parameter as well as other parameters. The starting point for determining the lag size was informed by the average NN distance for each study site, however lag sizes used in the models were often slightly smaller or larger than the average NN distance. For the majority of study sites, a standard neighborhood type with four sectors was used with the maximum and minimum neighbors being 15 and 10, respectively. Multiple kriging models were compared for each study site in order to minimize the mean standardized error, which should be near 0, and the root-mean-square standardized error, which should be near 1.

Table 3. Ordinary kriging parameters for contaminant study sites.

Study Sites	Variogram	Model Type	Major Range	Lag Size	Number of Lags	Neighborhood Type	Max Neighbors	Min Neighbors	Sectors
Arsenic									
1	Semivariogram	Stable	20266	2650	12	Standard	15	10	4
3	Semivariogram	Stable	10000	3385	12	Standard	15	10	4
6	Covariance	Stable	10	750	12	Standard	15	10	1
Uranium									
3	Semivariogram	Stable	10000	3650	12	Standard	15	10	4
4	Semivariogram	Stable	225	20	12	Standard	15	10	4
5	Semivariogram	Stable	25000	4500	12	Standard	15	10	1
Nitrate									
2	Semivariogram	Stable	7000	2500	12	Standard	15	10	4
4	Semivariogram	Stable	1500	100	12	Standard	15	10	4
6	Covariance	Stable	21250	2650	12	Standard	15	10	4

2.7 Model Evaluation

The model evaluation consisted of two parts: assessment of the model’s ability to accurately identify wells where an exceedance would occur, and the ease of use and ability to generate plausible, consistent results.

2.7.1 *Predictive power*

Predictive power was assessed in the same way for all four modeling approaches. The goal of this project is to develop methods to assist practitioners in identifying areas where there is a higher likelihood of elevated concentrations of a contaminant in private wells. As such, we focused on sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive power (PPV), and negative predictive power (NPV) as the most informative measures of predictive power. These statistics are derived by comparing two binary variables: whether the sample was above the threshold (yes/no) and whether the sample was predicted to be above the threshold (yes/no). Both the LUR and CART produce predicted probabilities that the sample is above the threshold, therefore a cut-off value needs to be selected to determine the probability associated with a predicted exceedance. If a very low value is chosen as the cut-off, sensitivity will be high (all the positives are captured) but specificity will be low (there will be many false positives). Selecting a high cut-off value will produce the opposite result. The choice of the cut-off point depends in part on the ‘cost’ of false negatives (not identifying wells that exceed the threshold leading to continuing exposure) versus the ‘cost’ of false positives (doing follow-up sampling on wells that aren’t actually above the threshold). If the model has good predictive power, then there are cut-off values

where both sensitivity and specificity are high. With less predictive models, there may not be any cut-off values with good sensitivity and specificity and the analyst must choose the 'best' point.

Our goal was to have a method which was very effective at identifying a high proportion of wells that had elevated concentrations, but that would not be seen as being overly 'alarmist.' To operationalize this goal, our criteria for selecting the cut-off was to maintain the sensitivity at 0.85 as long as the specificity was at least 0.70. If possible, the sensitivity would be increased as long as the specificity could be maintained at 0.75. When the model was not as good, we chose the best sensitivity while maintaining a minimum specificity of 0.70.

The perception of predictive power does depend on the choice of cut-off value. An overall measure of the predictive power is the area under the receiver-operator curve (AUC). Models with an $AUC \geq 0.9$ are considered excellent and models with an AUC 0.8 to 0.9 are considered good. A model with an AUC value of 0.5 is no better than a coin flip.

The geostatistical methods calculated predicted concentrations rather than predicted probabilities of exceeding a threshold concentration. We used this concentration in the same way, and assessed the sensitivity and specificity based on using each predicted concentration as the cut-off value. The cut-off value was selected using the same criteria as for the LUR and CART models.

2.7.2 *Qualitative evaluation*

Each modeling strategy was also evaluated based on several 'usability' factors, and these observations are discussed in Section 4 as part of the guidance to practitioners. The factors include the type of software needed, the complexity of running the models, level of statistical knowledge needed, and the ability of the modeling technique to produce models that 'make sense' and can be communicated to lay audiences.

3 Results

3.1 Arsenic

3.1.1 *Sample*

Study sites 1 (Intermontane Plateau), 3 (Interior Plains, Central Lowlands), and 6 (Wisconsin) were used for the development and assessment of ground water arsenic prediction models (Figure 4). More information about these study sites is presented in Appendix B. These sites were chosen to represent a variety of physiographic characteristics for areas where elevated As concentrations were regularly encountered. Elevated As concentrations occur more frequently in study site 1 (0.19) than study sites 3 (0.08) or 6 (0.04). However, study site 6 had the highest median value at 5.0 ppb (Table 4). Statistics describing all the explanatory variables are presented in Appendix C.

Figure 4. Study sites used for the assessment of As prediction models.

Table 4. Distribution of As concentrations by study site.

Site	N	Mean	% > 10 ppb	Min	P25	P50	P75	Max
1	6177	8.03	0.19	0.05	2.0	3.0	7.0	950
3	10967	3.06	0.08	0.05	0.25	0.70	2.6	661
6	3753	5.83	0.04	1.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	218

3.1.2 LUR modeling results

Model specification. The final LUR model specifications for As are presented in Table 5. The proportion of samples above the 10 ppb threshold were 0.19, 0.08 and 0.04 for study sites 1, 3, and 6, respectively. Given the final model, study site 3 had only 371 observations for which there was complete data. There are substantial differences between the final model specifications. Some of the data, such as well depth, were not available for the wells from Wisconsin (study site 6). The concentration of iron and pH are the only two variables that appear in the models for all three sites. The ORs associated with these variables differ substantially. Sulfate and alkalinity had the largest ORs in study site 1, whereas iron had an extraordinarily strong effect on the probability of elevated As in study site 3 (OR=21.5). Nitrate, iron, and alkalinity were all strong predictors for study site 6. However, increased alkalinity was associated with a decreased probability of elevated As in study site 6, as opposed to an increased probability of elevated As in study site 1. Pseudo-R² values were similar across the three models indicating similar predictive power.

Predictive power. Sensitivity ranged between 85 and 90% while specificity ranged between 70 and 75%. The AUC values indicated very good predictive power with values between 0.85 and 0.90. The only noticeable difference between the study sites is the variation in PPV; for study site 6 the PPV is only 8.5% indicating a very large number of wells predicted to be elevated which were not (Table 6).

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. Figures 5 – 7 depict the spatial distribution of areas where prediction was poor. In each figure the purple dots denote wells where the predicted category (i.e., greater than or less than the threshold) was different than the actual category. The top map denotes points where the true value was below 10 ppb while the lower map depicts well that were above 10 ppb.

In all three sites there are clusters of wells incorrectly predicted to be less than the 10 ppb threshold. It is not clear what aspects of these sites were responsible for the misclassification. No clustering of wells incorrectly classified as below 10 ppb was observed, however there were many fewer wells in this category.

Table 5. LUR parameter estimates for As study sites.

	Site 1	Site 3	Site 6
Explanatory Variables	As > 10 µg/l	As > 10 µg/l	As > 10 µg/l
pH			
<7.5	Ref	Ref	Ref
≥7.5	1.067	7.149**	2.143
Sulfate (mg/L)			
<10	Ref	Ref	
≥10	5.986***	2.910	
Phosphate (mg/L)			
<0.025	Ref	Ref	
≥0.025, <0.05	1.389*	3.333	
≥0.05	2.382***	1.064	
Nitrate (mg/L)			
<0.5	Ref		Ref
≥0.5	0.747		0.310***
Iron (µg/L)			
<100	Ref	Ref	Ref
≥100	1.257	21.49***	4.292**
Alkalinity (ueq/L)			
<10	Ref		Ref
≥10, <100	-		0.0143***
≥100, <150	2.900***		0.0968***
≥150, <200	1.741		0.147***
≥200, <250	2.838**		0.703
≥250	6.176***		-
Well Depth (ft)			
<100	Ref	Ref	
≥100, <300	0.968	9.802**	
≥300	0.585**	8.943*	

N	2801	371	3119
pseudo R-sq	0.287	0.256	0.302
Aic	1867.5	133.8	584.2
LI	-918.7	-57.91	-282.1

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001

Table 6. LUR As model performance.

	Site 1	Site 3	Site 6
Sensitivity	85.9	89.8	88.1
Specificity	73.4	75.0	70.8
PPV	50.9	27.3	8.5
NPV	94.2	98.6	99.5
AUC	0.85	0.87	0.90
Cut-point	0.16	0.06	0.02
LR Positive	3.2	3.6	3.0
LR Negative	0.2	0.1	0.2

Figure 5. Site 1 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using LUR.

Figure 6. Site 3 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using LUR.

Figure 7. Site 6 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using LUR.

3.1.3 CART model results

CART models. The final CART models for As study sites 1, 3, and 6 are found in Appendix D. In study site 1, PMPE (precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration, in inches/yr) was the primary classifying variable, with higher exceedances in drier environments. Phosphate and sulfate were the next two most important variables, with SO₄ acting within levels of PO₄ for higher PMPE, and PO₄ acting within SO₄ for the lowest PMPE category. In all cases the frequency of exceeding 10 ppb As

increased with increasing concentration of SO₄ or PO₄. pH had explanatory power when PO₄ was missing. Nineteen final categories were formed with the frequency of exceeding 10 ppb ranging from 0.78 to < 0.001.

At study site 3, pH was the primary driver (higher pH associated with higher As values) with iron acting as the next most important determinant for pH>7, demonstrating a positive association with As levels. At pH<7, well depth was the classifier with the frequency of exceedance increasing with depth. PO₄ was an important classifying variable with Fe when pH was missing. There were 18 nodes in the final model with frequency of exceedance ranging from <0.01 to 0.87.

A different pattern emerged from study site 6, where alkalinity was the primary driver with the frequency of exceedance increasing with increasing alkalinity. Fe, SO₄, NO₃, conductivity, and hardness all acted as predictors in different branches of the model. There were 26 nodes in the final model with the frequency of exceedance ranging from <0.01 to 0.37.

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. The distribution of misclassified wells across each study area is shown in Figures 8 - 10. There is a cluster of misclassified wells in the western part of the study site 6, similar to the pattern seen for the LUR model. There were no discernable patterns in the other study sites.

CART model performance. The performance of the CART models was similar across the three sites with good predictive power (AUC = 0.84 to 0.88). PPV values were 34% and 49% for study sites 3 and 1 respectively, but only 15% for study site 6 (Table 7).

Table 7. CART As model performance.

	Site 1	Site 3	Site 6
Sensitivity	85.7	86.1	90.0
Specificity	75.0	82.6	84.0
PPV	49.1	34.1	15.9
NPV	94.9	98.3	99.6
AUC	0.84	0.87	0.88
Cut-point	0.28	0.08	0.08
LR Positive	3.4	4.9	5.6
LR Negative	0.2	0.2	0.1

Figure 8. Site 1 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using CART.

Figure 9. Site 3 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using CART.

Figure 10. Site 6 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using CART.

3.1.4 Geostatistical results

The RMSE for IDW and ordinary kriging were similar for each As study site (Table 8). The spatial interpolations of As concentration using IDW and ordinary kriging resulted in large areas where the categorized As concentration was the same between the two interpolation methods (Figures 11 - 13). In study sites 1 and 6, there were wide areas where the ordinary kriging predicted levels were less than the IDW predicted levels. The two models produced very similar results for study site 3. Areas where

interpolation differences occurred were attributed to edge effects along study site borders, distribution and clustering of wells within the study sites (spatial structure), and the degree to which “neighbor” wells had similar As concentrations (spatial autocorrelation). All study sites had areas where wells with high As concentration were surrounded by wells with low As concentration (local maxima) and vice versa (local minima). In these local maxima areas, ordinary kriging will ‘smooth out’ the variation, which can result in underestimating As concentrations. This problem is less likely to occur with IDW since it is an exact interpolator and retains locally high and low concentration areas (hot spots and cool spots). Additional IDW and kriging output can be found in Appendix E.

Table 8. IDW and ordinary kriging results for As study sites.

Arsenic Study Site	IDW	Ordinary Kriging				
	RMSE	Mean	RMSE	Mean Standardized	Root Mean Square Standardized	Average Standard Error
1	13.33	-0.0184	13.8779	-0.0006	1.3903	9.7611
3	6.85	-0.0318	6.7995	-0.0036	0.7811	8.7161
6	3.66	0.0092	3.6407	0.0019	1.7366	5.7980

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. The distribution and location of correctly and incorrectly classified wells by each interpolation method is shown in Figures 14 - 19. In study site 1, there are clearly areas where both methods accurately predicted where the concentration was less than or greater than the 10 ppb threshold. There were also some patterns to the areas misclassified, however these were the same for each method. The misclassification patterns were also similar for IDW and ordinary kriging for both study sites 3 and 6. However, IDW had a much wider distribution of incorrectly classified wells below the 10 ppb threshold at both sites.

Model performance. Overall predictive power was very good with all but one AUC between 0.87 and 0.90. IDW at study site 6 had the poorest performance (Table 9). The PPV ranged considerably with study site 6 having PPV around 50%, while they were < 10% at the other two sites for both methods.

Table 9. Geostatistical model performance for As.

	IDW			Kriging		
	Site 1	Site 3	Site 6	Site 1	Site 3	Site 6
Sensitivity	85.3	88.1	78.9	86.0	84.7	86.8
Specificity	77.6	75.0	70.2	78.0	70.1	80.4
PPV	47.6	7.0	5.5	48.3	5.7	8.8
NPV	95.7	99.7	99.3	95.9	99.5	99.6
AUC	0.89	0.89	0.82	0.90	0.87	0.87
Cut-point	6.70	1.99	5.03	6.10	1.78	5.45
LR Positive	3.8	3.5	2.6	3.9	2.8	4.4
LR Negative	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2

Figure 11. Site 1 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of As concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Figure 12. Site 3 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of As concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Figure 13. Site 6 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of As concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Figure 14. .Site 1 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using IDW.

Figure 15. Site 1 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using ordinary kriging.

Figure16. Site 3 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using IDW.

Figure 17. Site 3 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using ordinary kriging.

Figure 18. Site 6 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using IDW.

Figure 19. Site 6 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified As wells using ordinary kriging.

3.1.5 *Comparison of Model Performance*

Overall, the methods were able to identify a high proportion of the wells in the validation dataset that had elevated arsenic. However, in doing so the methods also flagged a large number of wells that were not elevated. The four methods had similar ability to identify elevated wells with sensitivities ranging from 80 to 90%. Specificities were also similar across study sites and methods (70-80%), indicating that a significant proportion of negative wells were being identified as elevated. The P (i.e., proportion of those wells predicted to be elevated that actually were) varied the most between methods and study sites. For study site 1, the PPVs were close to 50% for all methods. At study site 3, the PPVs were approximately 30% for LUR and CART, but only 5-7% for the two geostatistical methods, indicating a large number of wells classified as elevated but not actually having elevated concentrations. For study site 6, the PPV for CART was 16%, higher than the other methods which ranged from 5.5% to 8.8%. CART did exhibit slightly better performance in study sites 3 and 6, having higher specificity and PPV. IDW performed less well at study site 6.

These measures depend on both the predictive power and the specific cut-off value used to distinguish between normal and elevated wells. The AUC reflects the overall predictive ability of the model. All of the methods demonstrated a good ability to discriminate between normal and elevated wells at all study sites with AUC values ranging between 0.82 and 0.90 (Table 10). There were no striking differences in performance or between methods across study sites.

Table 10. Comparison of LUR, CART, IDW and KRIG for predicting elevated As concentrations greater than 10 ppb.

		LUR	CART	IDW	KRIG
Site 1	Sensitivity	85.9	85.7	85.3	86.0
	Specificity	73.4	75.0	77.6	78.0
	PPV	50.9	49.1	47.6	48.3
	NPV	94.2	94.9	95.7	95.9
	AUC	0.85	0.84	0.89	0.90
	Cut-point	0.16	0.28	6.70	6.10
	LR Positive	3.2	3.4	3.8	3.9
	LR Negative	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Site 3	Sensitivity	89.8	86.1	88.1	84.7
	Specificity	75.0	82.6	75.0	70.1
	PPV	27.3	34.1	7.0	5.7
	NPV	98.6	98.3	99.7	99.5
	AUC	0.87	0.87	0.89	0.87
	Cut-point	0.06	0.08	1.99	1.78
	LR Positive	3.6	4.9	3.5	2.8
	LR Negative	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2
Site 6	Sensitivity	88.1	90.0	78.9	86.8
	Specificity	70.8	84.0	70.2	80.4
	PPV	8.5	15.9	5.5	8.8
	NPV	99.5	99.6	99.3	99.6
	AUC	0.90	0.88	0.82	0.87
	Cut-point	0.02	0.08	5.03	5.45
	LR Positive	3.0	5.6	2.6	4.4
	LR Negative	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.2

3.1.6 *Conclusion*

All the methods had good to very good predictive power (AUC= 0.8 to 0.9) with high sensitivity and good to moderate specificity. There were no meaningful differences between the predictive abilities of the four methods. CART did have slightly better predictive power for study site 6. Overall, PPVs were low, indicating a large proportion of wells below the threshold being classified as exceeding the threshold.

3.2 Uranium

3.2.1 *Sample*

Study sites 3 (Interior Plains, Central Lowlands, Osage Plains), 4 (Interior Plains, Great Plains, High Plains & Colorado Piedmont) and 5 (California Central Valley) were used for the development and assessment of groundwater U prediction models (Figure 20). More information about these study sites is presented in Appendix B. These sites were chosen to represent a variety of physiographic characteristics for areas where elevated U were regularly encountered.

Elevated U concentrations (≥ 15 ppb) occurred more frequently in study sites 4 (0.20) and 5 (0.22) than in study site 3 (0.12). Study site 4 had the highest concentrations overall, including the largest 25th percentile value and median value (Table 11). Study site 5 had fewer observations than the other study sites. Statistics describing all the explanatory variables are presented in Appendix C.

Figure 20. Study sites used for the assessment of U prediction models

Table 11. Distribution of U concentrations by study site.

Site	N	Mean	% > 10 ppb	Min	P25	P50	P75	Max
3	7809	7.33	0.12	0.01	0.48	2.24	7.2	1500
4	5960	20.6	0.20	0.01	2.94	6.10	11.9	5720
5	1611	20.5	0.22	0.01	0.70	3.14	12.4	3085

3.2.2 *LUR Model results*

Model specification. The final LUR model specifications for U are presented in Table 12. The concentration of U in surficial deposits (as measured by airborne gamma-ray spectrometry) and soil infiltration rate were directly associated with the probability of U > 15 ppb, while well depth was inversely related. Increased sulfate, iron, arsenic, alkalinity, and specific conductance were associated with the increased probability of elevated U, while the probability decreased with increasing pH. As with the other LUR models, the variables included depended strongly on the availability of data. Phosphate, for example, was measured only in a small number of samples. The model for study site 5 had the best fit with a pseudo-R² of 0.30.

Predictive power. The uranium LUR models had moderate predictive power with AUC values ranging from 0.78 to 0.84. Model sensitivities, which were subject to having a specificity at or above 0.7, were only 0.75 for study sites 3 and 4, and 0.83 for study site 5. Study site 5 had the best model performance, with a PPV of 44%, indicating that almost one out of every two wells predicted to have elevated U would actually have elevated uranium (Table 13).

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. Figures 21 – 23 depict the spatial distribution of areas where prediction was poor. In each figure the purple dots denote wells where the predicted category (i.e., greater than or less than the threshold) was different than the actual category. The top map denotes points where the true value was below 15 ppb while the lower map depicts well that were above 15 ppb.

In study site 3, there is a striking pattern where there was no misclassification of wells below the threshold in the eastern and northern part of the study area, and little misclassification of elevated U in the southern part of the study site. Study site 4 had no discernable pattern of classification error. In study site 5, misclassification of wells below the 15 ppb threshold was focused in the southern part of the area. The pattern of misclassification in study site 3, and to a lesser extent in study site 5, may be the result of a very strong set of predictors that work well in one area, but which are confounded by an unmeasured factor in the areas to the south and west (Figures 21-23).

Table 12. LUR parameter estimates for U study sites.

	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5
pH			
<7.5		Ref	Ref
≥7.5		0.658**	0.561**
Sulfate (mg/L)			
<10	Ref	Ref	
≥10	1.871*	12.12***	
Alkalinity (ueq/L)			
<150		Ref	
≥150, <250		1.606*	
≥250		3.710***	
Aeroradiometric U equivalent concentration			
<1.5	Ref	Ref	Ref
≥1.5	1.592***	1.840***	3.328***
Percent soil w/in 500m that is moderate/high infiltration			
<95	Ref	Ref	Ref
≥95	1.436***	1.708***	3.563***
Mean annual PMPE (inches/year)			
<-10	Ref	Ref	
≥10, <0	0.577***	0.640	
≥0	0.235***		
Arsenic, Dissolved (µg/l)			
<10	Ref		
≥10	3.659***		
Iron, Dissolved (µg/l)			
<15	Ref	Ref	
≥15	1.368**	1.843***	
Specific Conductance (ueq/L)			
<500	Ref		Ref
≥500, <1000	1.623		8.637***
>1000	5.997***		15.55***
Well Depth (ft)			
<100	Ref	Ref	Ref
≥100, <300	0.901	0.449***	1.033
≥300	0.624	0.332***	0.418*

N	4655	3113	1013
pseudo R-sq	0.180	0.194	0.299
Aic	2949.7	1931.8	775.9
LI	-1459.8	-951.9	-378.9

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001

Table13. LUR U model performance.

	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5
Sensitivity	75.6	75.4	82.5
Specificity	69.9	70.1	70.1
PPV	29.0	27.4	43.9
NPV	94.6	95.0	93.4
AUC	0.78	0.82	0.84
Cut-point	0.15	0.14	0.16
LR Positive	3.2	3.6	3.0
LR Negative	0.2	0.1	0.2

Figure 21. Site 3 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using LUR.

Figure 22. Site 4 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using LUR.

Figure 23. Site 5 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using LUR.

3.2.3 CART model results

CART models. . The final CART models for U study sites 3, 4, and 5 are found in Appendix D. At study site 3, Precipitation minus Potential Evapotranspiration (PMPE) was the primary driver, with the proportion of samples above the threshold decreasing with increasing PMPE. Sulfate was the most important secondary driver at almost every level of PMPE. Exceedances increased with increasing SO₄ and As concentrations as well as with increasing specific conductance. This model was complex. There were 40 terminal nodes with the proportion of samples greater than 15 ppb ranging from 0 to 64%.

Well depth was the primary driver for study site 4; 48% of the samples from the shallowest wells (<38.5 ft) had U concentrations above 15 ppb, dropping to 6% among wells >200 ft deep. SO4 was the next most explanatory factor at all levels of well depth. There were 25 terminal nodes with exceedance rates ranging from 1.5 to 80.5%.

The study site 5 CART model was different from the models for the other two sites. Iron concentration was the primary driver. There was a strong positive relationship with the proportion of samples above 15 ppb, ranging from 7.1 to 58.2%. Phosphate was important at the lowest Fe concentration category (positive relationship) while PMPE was important at the lowest PO4 concentration category or when PO4 data were not available (inverse relationship). This model has only 11 terminal nodes with the proportion samples above the U threshold ranging from 1.5 to 58.2%.

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. The distribution of misclassified wells has similar patterns to those seen for the LUR model, although there are some misclassified wells in areas that were correctly classified by the LUR model (Figures 24 -26). In study site 3, the misclassified wells are clustered towards the east, indicating that the relationship between the explanatory variables and the outcome varies substantially within the study site, and/or that data describing relevant explanatory factors for these parts of the study site were not available.

Cart model performance. The predictive power of the CART models is similar to the LUR models; sensitivities range from 73 to 83% when constraining the specificities to 70% or better. The AUC values are good (0.81-0.87). At study site 3, the PPV is just under 30%, indicating that approximately only one in three wells identified as being potentially contaminated actually would be. At study sites 4 and 5, the PPV was close to 50% (Table 14).

Table 14. CART U model performance

	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5
Sensitivity	75.1	83.5	73.1
Specificity	73.3	75.0	78.4
PPV	29.7	45.1	48.3
NPV	95.1	94.9	91.3
AUC	0.81	0.87	0.84
Cut-point	0.11	0.09	0.17
LR Positive	3.4	4.9	5.6
LR Negative	0.2	0.2	0.1

Figure 24. Site 3 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using CART.

Figure 25. Site 4 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using CART.

Figure 26. Site 5 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using CART.

3.2.4 Geostatistical results

The RMSE for IDW and ordinary kriging were similar for each U study site (Table 15). The level of agreement between the two interpolation methods resulted in large areas where the categorized U concentration was the same between the two interpolation methods (Figures 27 - 29). In study site 3, there are few areas where the predicted levels are in different concentration categories. In study sites 4 and 5, there are substantial areas where the kriging predictions are higher or lower than the IDW. Areas

where interpolation differences occurred across U study sites were attributed to edge effects along study site borders, distribution and clustering of wells within the study sites (spatial structure), and the degree to which “neighbor” wells had similar uranium concentrations (spatial autocorrelation). All study sites had areas where wells with high U concentration were surrounded by wells with low U concentration (local maxima) and vice versa (local minima). In these local maxima areas, ordinary kriging will ‘smooth out’ the variation, which can result in underestimating U concentrations. In the southern part of study site 5, kriging generates much lower concentrations than IDW, likely reflecting areas of localized elevations in U levels. This problem is less likely to occur with IDW since it is an exact interpolator and retains locally high and low concentration areas (hot spots and cool spots). Additional IDW and kriging output can be found in Appendix E.

Table 15. IDW and ordinary kriging results for U study sites.

Uranium Study Sites	IDW	Ordinary Kriging				
	RMSE	Mean	RMSE	Mean Standardized	Root Mean Square Standardized	Average Standard Error
3	13.22	-0.0051	13.9047	-0.0003	0.8399	16.5857
4	25.26	0.0059	23.4155	-0.0008	0.2697	100.8353
5	44.02	0.1970	42.3828	0.0033	1.0550	40.9384

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. The distribution and location of correctly and incorrectly classified wells by each interpolation method is shown in Figures 30 - 35. The patterns of misclassified wells are similar for both geostatistical methods as well as to the LUR and CART model patterns. The areas where there are no misclassified wells is not as striking with these models as for the LUR models, however there are still areas devoid of misclassified wells in the eastern part of study site 3 and northern part of study site 5.

Model performance. The two geostatistical methods both had moderately good predictive power with AUC values between 0.76 and 0.84 (Table 16). Sensitivity values were lower for study site 5, especially for IDW (sensitivity=70.6%). IDW did produce higher sensitivity and PPV values in all three sites than did ordinary kriging.

Table 16. Geostatistical model performance for U.

	IDW			Kriging		
	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5
Sensitivity	83.2	82.8	70.6	80.2	81.7	77.1
Specificity	70.0	70.0	67.0	67.9	70.0	70.2
PPV	40.8	50.7	46.4	26.9	34.4	39.8
NPV	94.4	91.6	84.9	95.9	95.2	92.3
AUC	0.84	0.84	0.76	0.82	0.83	0.81
Cut-point	5.95	8.34	12.75	7.17	9.68	11.40
LR Positive	3.8	3.5	2.6	3.9	2.8	4.4
LR Negative	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2

Figure 27. Site 3 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of U concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Figure 28. Site 4 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of U concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Figure 29. Site 5 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of U concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Figure 30. Site 3 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using IDW.

Figure 31. Site 3 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using ordinary kriging.

Figure 32. Site 4 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using IDW.

Figure 33. Site 4 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using ordinary kriging.

Figure 34. Site 5 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using IDW.

Figure 35. Site 5 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified U wells using ordinary kriging.

3.2.5 Comparison of models

For study sites 3 and 4, all the predictors in the CART model were also significant predictors in the final LUR model. Aeroradiometric U equivalent concentration and percent of soil around the well, which had moderate or high infiltration, were both significant predictors for all three sites in the LUR models, but were not identified as important predictors using CART.

For study site 5, the CART and LUR models used completely different explanatory variables. Specific conductance, soil infiltration, and aeroradiometric U concentration were significant predictors; the CART model only included Fe concentration, PO₄ concentration, and PMPE. Phosphate was a significant predictor in the LUR models, but there were relatively few observations so that including PO₄ reduced the effective sample size substantially.

The predictive power of all methods for all study sites is presented in Table 17. There are no clear patterns to suggest that one method is superior to the rest. When the specificity was constrained to be 70% or better, the sensitivities ranged from 71% to 83%. The geospatial methods had higher sensitivities for study site 3, and IDW had a substantially higher PPV (40.8%) than the other methods (range = 26.9 to 29.7%). For study site 4, LUR underperformed relative to the other methods with lower sensitivity and PPV. In contrast, LUR had substantially higher sensitivity for study site 6 than the other methods.

Table 17. Comparison of LUR, CART, IDW and KRIG for predicting elevated U concentrations greater than 15 ppb.

		LUR	CART	IDW	KRIG
Site 3	Sensitivity	75.6	75.1	83.2	80.2
	Specificity	69.9	73.3	70.0	67.9
	PPV	29.0	29.7	40.8	26.9
	NPV	94.6	95.1	94.4	95.9
	AUC	0.78	0.81	0.84	0.82
	Prevalence	14.0	13.1	19.9	12.9
	Cut-point	0.15	0.11	5.95	7.17
Site 4	Sensitivity	75.4	83.5	82.8	81.7
	Specificity	70.1	75.0	70.0	70.0
	PPV	27.4	45.1	50.7	34.4
	NPV	95.0	94.9	91.6	95.2
	AUC	0.82	0.87	0.84	0.83
	Prevalence	13.0	19.7	27.2	16.1
	Cut-point	0.14	0.09	8.34	9.68
Site 5	Sensitivity	82.5	73.1	70.6	77.1
	Specificity	70.1	78.4	67.0	70.2
	PPV	43.9	48.3	46.4	39.8
	NPV	93.4	91.3	84.9	92.3
	AUC	0.84	0.84	0.76	0.81
	Prevalence	22.1	21.7	28.8	20.3
	Cut-point	0.16	0.17	12.75	11.40

3.2.6 Conclusion

All four methods generally demonstrated good predictive power with AUC>0.80 in 10 of the 12 assessments. The relative performance varied with study site. The explanatory factors identified in the LUR and CART models were similar for two of the study sites, but for site 5, different factors were identified by the two methods. There were striking patterns of misclassification. Regardless of method, there was no misclassification of wells under the threshold for the eastern side of study site 3 and the northern half of study site 5. This may indicate that for the areas with misclassification an important explanatory variable is missing.

3.3 Nitrate

3.3.1 Sample

Study sites 2 (Atlantic Coastal Plain, Embayed), 4 (Interior Plains, Great Plains, High Plains & Colorado Piedmont) and 6 (Wisconsin) were used for the development and assessment of groundwater nitrate prediction models (Figure 36). These sites were chosen to represent a variety of physiographic characteristics for areas where elevated NO₃-N concentrations were regularly encountered. In addition, study sites 2 and 4 were chosen because they have a large number of NO₃-N samples, and a high proportion of those samples are above 10 mg/l NO₃-N. Wisconsin was chosen because of the availability of a large database of groundwater nitrate concentrations. More information about these study sites is presented in Appendix B.

Figure 36. Study sites used for the assessment of NO₃-N prediction models

The proportion of wells with NO₃-N concentrations above 10 mg/l ranges from 7% (study site 2) to 17% (study site 4). Study site 4 has the smallest sample size but the highest mean and median nitrate values (Table 18). The WI database has a large number of observations, but many of the wells lack geochemical data. Statistics describing all the explanatory variables are presented in Appendix C.

Table 18. Distribution of NO₃-N concentrations by study site

Site	N	Mean	% > 10 ppm	Min	P25	P50	P75	Max
2	3467	3.19	0.07	0.01	0.03	0.83	4.00	62.0
4	1848	6.58	0.17	0.01	2.12	5.04	7.93	106.0
6	7637	3.76	0.11	0.05	0.05	1.20	5.20	49.0

3.3.2 LUR Model results

Model specification. The final LUR models for NO₃-N are presented in Table 19. Most of the same factors appear in all models, however the specific variable measuring the factors varies between models. The actual sample used for the models was reduced in each case because of missing data. In general, only pH and conductivity were available for enough samples to include them in the models. The pseudo-R² values were much higher for the study site 2 and 4 models.

Predictive power. The predictive power of these models was only moderate. AUC values ranged from 0.75 to 0.81 (Table 20), and the sensitivities were under 75% when the specificities were kept at about 70%. PPVs were variable and low, ranging from 19.6 to 27.9 %.

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. Figures 37 – 39 depict the spatial distribution of areas where prediction was poor. In each figure the purple dots denote wells where the predicted category (i.e., greater than or less than the threshold) was different than the actual category. The top map denotes points where the true value was below 10 ppm while the lower map depicts well that were above 10 ppm. There were no striking patterns in the location of wells that were misclassified (Figures 37 - 39).

Table 19. LUR parameter estimates for NO₃-N study sites

	Site 2	Site 4	Site 6
Nitrogen application rate			
% of 500 m buffer > 100 lb/acre	1.034***	1.024***	
% of 500 m buffer 50 – 100 lb/acre	1.049*		
Farm fertilizer application rate (county level)		1.000*	
Non-farm fertilizer application rate (county level, lbs/acre)	0.999*		1.001
Well Depth (ft)		0.996*	
Well Depth, categorical			
0 – 100 ft	Ref		
> 100 ft	0.318*		
Precipitation (in) during month	0.974**	1.011	
Precipitation in previous month (in)			0.996**
Average precipitation (in)			1.797***
Potential evapotranspiration (in)	0.721*		1.938***
Frequency of flooding	1.082**	1.045***	
% area with 500 m that is intermittent lake	0.816		
% area within 500 m that is water			0.963
Frequency of ponding		0.923	
Population density (persons / sq mi)			
< 1	Ref	Ref	
1 – <= 500	0.229**	Ref	
> 500	0.164*	3.327**	
% of 500 m buffer urban		0.529	
pH	0.286***	0.285**	0.836
Specific conductance (meq/l)		1.001***	1.002***
% lowland that is flat	0.983*		
Slope		1.203**	0.972*
Minimum elevation (ft)			1.003*
% soil ‘well or excessively drained’	1.012		
% soil that is sand (top 2 m)	0.976	0.979*	1.004
% soil that is mod/high infiltration	0.995	1.031**	
Average temperature (C)			0.694***

N	1002	919	4695
pseudo R-sq	0.385	0.312	0.1
Aic	383.9	583.9	2961
LI	175.9	-277	-1468.5

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001

Table 20. LUR NO3-N model performance

	Site 2	Site 4	Site 6
Sensitivity	74.1	74.6	70.9
Specificity	70.0	70.2	68.5
PPV	23.7	27.9	19.6
NPV	95.6	94.7	95.6
AUC	0.81	0.81	0.75
Cut-point	0.05	0.11	0.11
LR Positive	2.5	2.5	2.3
LR Negative	0.4	0.4	0.4

Figure 37. Site 2 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO3-N wells using LUR.

Figure 38. Site 4 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO3-N wells using LUR.

Figure 39. Site 6 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO₃-N wells using LUR.

3.3.3 CART model results

CART models. The final CART models for NO₃-N study sites 2, 4, and 6 are found in Appendix D. The estimated nitrogen application rate around the well was the primary classifying variable. The 500 m well buffers that had more than 30% of the area covered by crops with high nitrogen needs were elevated more frequently (25%) than the 500 m well buffers covered by crops with less estimated nitrogen needs (5%). The factors associated with a high proportion of elevated wells at the second level

of the tree were increased soil drainage, increased population density, and increased average fertilizer application rates. Precipitation, well depth, percent sand in the soil, and SO₄ were used in the third and fourth levels. The final model had 23 nodes with the frequency of exceedance ranging from 0.3% to 70%.

Conductivity was the primary driver for study sites 4 and 6. For study site 4, precipitation, irrigation, fertilizer loading, and population density were included in the model. In contrast, the model for study site 6 was dominated by geochemical parameters: pH, chloride, and alkalinity. The study site 4 model had 23 nodes, and the proportion of wells with elevated nitrate at each terminal node ranged from 0% to 97%. The study site 6 model was more complex with 33 nodes, and the proportion of elevated wells within a terminal node ranged from 0 to 58%.

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. Misclassification of wells, either as ‘elevated’ or as ‘not elevated’, occurred throughout the parts of the study regions where wells were located (Figures 40-42).

CART model performance. Overall predictive power of these models was moderate with AUC at only 0.73 for study site 2, and 0.84 for the two other sites. Sensitivity was about 72%, indicating that the model failed to identify over a quarter of the elevated wells. In study site 4, the PPV was 49% but was low in the other two sites (Table 21).

Table 21. CART NO₃-N model performance

	Site 2	Site 4	Site 6
Sensitivity	72.7	72.8	73.6
Specificity	71.4	85.4	75.7
PPV	16.1	49.3	26.0
NPV	97.2	94.2	96.1
AUC	0.73	0.83	0.83
Cut-point	0.03	0.10	0.20
LR Positive	2.5	5.0	3.0
LR Negative	0.4	0.3	0.3

Figure 40. Site 2 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO₃-N wells using CART.

Figure 41. Site 4 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO3-N wells using CART.

Figure 42. Site6 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO₃-N wells using CART.

3.3.4 Geostatistical results

The RMSE for IDW and ordinary kriging were similar for each NO₃-N study site (Table 22). The level of agreement between the two interpolation methods resulted in large areas where the categorized NO₃-N concentration was the same between the two interpolation methods (Figures 43 - 45). In study site 2, there are few areas where the predicted levels are in different concentration categories. In study sites 4 and 6, there are substantial areas where the kriging predictions are higher or

lower than the IDW. Areas where interpolation differences occurred across the NO₃-N study sites were attributed to edge effects along study site borders, distribution and clustering of wells within the study sites (spatial structure), and the degree to which “neighbor” wells had similar NO₃-N concentrations (spatial autocorrelation). All study sites had areas where wells with high NO₃-N concentration were surrounded by wells with low NO₃-N concentration (local maxima) and vice versa (local minima). In these local maxima areas, ordinary kriging will ‘smooth out’ the variation, which can result in underestimating NO₃-N concentrations. In study site 4, kriging generates much lower concentrations than IDW, likely reflecting areas of localized elevations in NO₃-N levels. This problem is less likely to occur with IDW since it is an exact interpolator and retains locally high and low concentration areas (hot spots and cool spots). Additional IDW and kriging output can be found in Appendix E.

Table 22. IDW and ordinary kriging results for NO₃-N study sites.

Nitrate Study Sites	IDW	Ordinary Kriging				
	RMSE	Mean	RMSE	Mean Standardized	Root Mean Square Standardized	Average Standard Error
2	4.37	0.0062	4.3339	0.0002	0.9989	4.6601
4	13.13	-0.0939	13.0526	-0.0044	0.6124	29.4461
6	4.17	0.0069	4.0510	0.0011	1.1276	3.7513

Spatial distribution of misclassification errors. The two interpolation methods produced similar spatial patterns in the location of misclassified wells (Figures 46 - 51). Among wells that were below the NO₃-N threshold of 10 mg/l, there was far more misclassification in the northern area of study site 2 and central area of study site 4. There are no strong patterns of misclassification for study site 6.

Model performance. The overall predictive power of the two interpolation methods was considered good (AUC=0.8 to 0.85). Sensitivity and PPV varied across sites, but there were few differences between methods (Table 23).

Figure 43. Site 2 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of NO₃-N concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Figure 44. Site 4 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of NO₃-N concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Figure 45. Site 6 - differences between IDW and kriging interpolations of NO₃-N concentration based on concentration categories. The purple area is where the ordinary kriging category was the same as the IDW category.

Table 23. Geostatistical model performance for NO₃-N

	IDW			Kriging		
	Site 2	Site 4	Site 6	Site 2	Site 4	Site 6
Sensitivity	85.2	82.0	78.2	85.2	76.4	79.1
Specificity	70.0	64.5	70.0	70.1	70.0	70.0
PPV	18.9	37.1	22.2	18.9	39.4	22.4
NPV	98.3	93.3	96.7	98.3	92.1	96.8
AUC	0.86	0.80	0.81	0.85	0.79	0.82
Cut-point	3.21	6.40	4.16	3.12	6.64	4.11
LR Positive	2.8	2.3	2.6	2.8	2.5	2.6
LR Negative	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.3

Figure 46. Site 2 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO3-N wells using IDW.

Figure 47. Site 2 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO₃-N wells using kriging.

Figure 48. Site 4 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO3-N wells using IDW.

Figure 49. Site 4 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO3-N wells using kriging.

Figure 50. Site 6 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO3-N wells using IDW.

Figure 51. Site 6 - distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified NO3-N wells using kriging.

3.3.5 Comparison of models

There were few substantial differences in predictive power between the four methods (Table 24). The geostatistical interpolation methods did have somewhat higher sensitivity levels than LUR or CART (when constraining the specificity to be near 0.70). The differences between the highest sensitivity of the LUR and CART models compared to the highest sensitivity of the two interpolation methods were 0.11, 0.08, and 0.05 for study sites 2, 4, and 6, respectively. PPV were all low, less than 0.25 for study

sites 2 and 6. In study site 4, CART had the highest PPV at 49.3% and LUR was the lowest at 27.9%. The two geostatistical methods had nearly the same PPV (37.1% and 39.4%). Across all sites, the AUC values clustered around 0.80, the lower level of what is considered to be good predictive power.

Table 24. Comparison of LUR, CART, IDW and KRIG for predicting elevated NO₃-N concentrations.

		LUR	CART	IDW	KRIG
Site 2	Sensitivity	74.1	72.7	85.2	85.2
	Specificity	70.0	71.4	70.0	70.1
	PPV	23.7	16.1	18.9	18.9
	NPV	95.6	97.2	98.3	98.3
	AUC	0.81	0.73	0.86	0.85
	Prevalence	11.2	7.0	7.6	7.6
	Cut-point	0.05	0.03	3.21	3.12
Site 4	Sensitivity	74.6	72.8	82.0	76.4
	Specificity	70.2	85.4	64.5	70.0
	PPV	27.9	49.3	37.1	39.4
	NPV	94.7	94.2	93.3	92.1
	AUC	0.81	0.83	0.80	0.79
	Prevalence	13.4	16.3	20.3	20.3
	Cut-point	0.11	0.10	6.40	6.64
Site 6	Sensitivity	70.9	73.6	78.2	79.1
	Specificity	68.5	75.7	70.0	70.0
	PPV	19.6	26.0	22.2	22.4
	NPV	95.6	96.1	96.7	96.8
	AUC	0.75	0.83	0.81	0.82
	Prevalence	9.8	10.4	9.9	9.9
	Cut-point	0.11	0.20	4.16	4.11

3.3.6 Conclusion

The mean AUC value was 0.81; the AUC was less than 0.75 in two of the nine case studies. The two geostatistical methods had slightly better sensitivity than LUR or CART for all three sites. AUC values for the geostatistical methods were higher only for study site 2. Overall, there were no substantial differences in predictive power between the four methods

3.4 Comparison across contaminants

The sensitivity, PPV, and AUC for all contaminants, sites, and methods are presented in Table 25. Overall, there were few differences in the predictive ability across the four methods and the three contaminants. Mean sensitivity when the specificity was above 0.70 was 80.6% (range = 79.2% - 81.9%). However, wells classified as 'elevated' were over three times as likely to be elevated as not. Of the 36 case studies (three contaminants x three study sites x four methods), sensitivity was between 70% and 75% in 8 (22%) and above 80 in 20 (55%). Average sensitivity for models predicting arsenic (86.3%) was somewhat better than for uranium (78.4%) or nitrate (77.1%). The sensitivity of the CART method was more variable; in four of the nine case studies the sensitivity was less than 75%. While IDW and kriging had higher average sensitivities, kriging was more consistent with no values under 76.0%.

PPVs were modest (average = 30.4%), reflecting the significant number of wells that were misclassified as 'elevated.' PPV values were similar across methods, even when the two anomalous results (arsenic study sites 3 and 6) were not included. There was more PPV variability across study sites than for sensitivity or AUC. CART had a slightly higher average PPV, which is not surprising given the lower sensitivity of the method.

The AUC is a measure of predictive value which, unlike sensitivity and PPV, is not affected by the cut-off value. AUC values ranged from 0.73 to 0.90 with an overall mean of 0.83 (good); 31 of the 36 case studies had AUC values above 0.80. Model performance did vary for any given method between study sites and between contaminants (max difference in AUC between sites or within contaminants = 0.10). Average AUC values for each method were almost identical, and each method had the best predictive power (i.e., highest AUC value) and worst power (i.e., lowest AUC value) among the four methods in at least of one of the nine case studies.

Table 25. Comparison across contaminants.

Contaminant	Site	Sensitivity				PPV				AUC			
		LUR	CART	IDW	KRIG	LUR	CART	IDW	KRIG	LUR	CART	IDW	KRIG
As	1	85.9	85.7	85.3	86	50.9	49.1	47.6	48.3	0.85	0.84	0.89	0.90
As	3	89.8	86.1	88.1	84.7	27.3	34.1	7	5.7	0.87	0.87	0.89	0.87
As	6	88.1	90	78.9	86.8	8.5	15.9	5.5	8.8	0.90	0.88	0.82	0.87
U	3	75.6	75.1	83.2	80.2	29	29.7	40.8	26.9	0.78	0.81	0.84	0.82
U	4	75.4	83.5	82.8	81.7	27.4	45.1	50.7	34.4	0.82	0.87	0.84	0.83
U	5	82.5	73.1	70.6	77.1	43.9	48.3	46.4	39.8	0.84	0.84	0.76	0.81
NO3	2	74.1	72.7	85.2	85.2	23.7	16.1	18.9	18.9	0.81	0.73	0.86	0.85
NO3	4	74.6	72.8	82	76.4	27.9	49.3	37.1	39.4	0.81	0.83	0.80	0.79
NO3	6	70.9	73.6	78.2	79.1	19.6	26	22.2	22.4	0.75	0.83	0.81	0.82
	mean	79.7	79.2	81.6	81.9	28.7	34.8	30.7	27.2	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.84
	range	18.9	17.3	17.5	10.4	42.4	33.4	45.2	42.6	0.15	0.15	0.13	0.11
	min	70.9	72.7	70.6	76.4	8.5	15.9	5.5	5.7	0.75	0.73	0.76	0.79
	stddev	7.0	7.0	5.2	3.9	12.5	13.8	17.6	14.6	0.046	0.045	0.042	0.035

4 Guidance for Use and Recommendations for Further Development

The overall purpose of this project was to develop data and tools to help public health practitioners identify areas with a high likelihood of elevated arsenic, uranium, or nitrate concentrations, which would assist them in targeting outreach and confirmatory sampling. The first product is the National Screening Model, which is a series of county-level maps covering the conterminous US with predictions of arsenic, uranium, and nitrate concentrations within 4 km of a well as well as predicted probabilities of exceedance for other areas (see Figures 52 - 54 for examples). The predictions were generated from a national CART model. For most counties, there was sufficient data to generate predictions for nearly all areas where private well use is likely. Access to these maps and documentation about the methods used to produce them can be obtained by emailing Jim VanDerslice at jim.vanderslice@utah.edu.

The accuracy of any of the four methods evaluated in this report is limited by the spatial coverage of wells with groundwater quality data as well as the availability of site specific characteristics and geochemical data. As discussed in Section 3.4, there were few differences in the predictive ability of the four methods. Predictive power did vary somewhat by contaminant and study site, so for any specific study site, contaminant, and dataset, any of the methods could possibly provide the best predictions depending on the level of information available to the agency or analyst. Some agencies may have access to additional local data or may wish to develop and apply their own prediction models.

The two geostatistical interpolation methods, IDW and ordinary kriging, have the advantage of needing only good location information and the concentration of the target contaminant(s). Both methods can be carried out using routines in ArcGIS with an advanced GIS user. There is good documentation to guide the use of these methods. Kriging did not perform better than IDW, and was observed to smooth out local areas of high or low concentrations. Kriging is also more complicated to use. As such, we recommend the use of IDW because it is easier to use, easier to explain, and because it can capture local 'hot' and 'cool' spots. However, the advantage of ordinary kriging is that it can provide a measure of prediction accuracy in terms of a standard error of the prediction for each point in the area of interest. Kriging could also be used in conjunction with IDW to give a sense of the accuracy of the predictions. The primary limitation of IDW or kriging is that the accuracy of the predictions is a function of distance from the nearest well(s) with contaminant data; accurate predictions are not possible if there are no such wells in an area.

Figure 52. Example of an arsenic county-level screening map, Clarion County, PA.

Figure 53. Example of a uranium county-level screening map, Fresno County, CA.

Figure 54. Example of a nitrate county-level screening map, Lancaster County, PA.

With geochemical data, LUR can be used to predict concentrations for wells that have chemical data but are lacking data for the target contaminants. In our work, we had many wells with data for basic geochemical parameters even if they lacked arsenic, uranium and/or nitrate concentrations. This increases the number of wells/locations where predicted values can be generated. However, these predictions are still just for points and interpolation, such as IDW, needs to be used to ‘fill in the gaps’ between the wells. LUR also requires statistical software and someone with experience creating statistical models. As a result, LUR may only be worth the effort if there are large areas where there are no wells with data on arsenic/uranium, but there are wells for which relevant geochemical data exist.

CART is an alternative to LUR. CART has the advantage of creating models that are flexible in the effects that factors can have on predictions and it intuitively makes sense. However, the software is difficult to use and requires a person with at least intermediate statistical skills. CART has the same

limitations with arsenic and uranium models as LUR, i.e., predictions are still just for points and interpolation, such as IDW, needs to be used to interpolate between the wells.

Nitrate models were based on site characteristics, not geochemical data from wells, which enabled predictions to be made for any location where site data existed and were similar to the areas where the models were developed. With nitrate, we were able to predict into PWUAs based on these site characteristics and models; this was not possible with arsenic and uranium. Basing predictions on site-specific information necessitates the need to generate these data for virtually all areas in PWUAs. We have already compiled and processed such information for a large number of important predictors of groundwater nitrate levels (see Appendix A). We may be able to share these data (depending on data use restrictions), or at least work with other practitioners to use these data. Other site specific information at the state or local level may be available to be used to create potentially better predictive models.

The National Screening Model for identifying private wells with a high likelihood of elevated concentrations provides a good set of predictions to help identify areas to target for outreach and/or sampling. If practitioners wish to develop their own models because they have additional data, we recommend using IDW for its simplicity and transparency. LUR or CART may be worthwhile if data on the contaminant of concern are sparse and/or a nitrate model using site specific information to predict into larger areas.

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

In this study, we developed and evaluated four methods for predicting areas where groundwater concentrations of arsenic, uranium, or nitrate were elevated using split-sample validation at three sites for each contaminant. Overall, there were few differences in the predictive ability across the four methods and the three contaminants. AUC values ranged from 0.73 to 0.90 with an overall mean of 0.83 (good); 31 of the 36 case studies had AUC values above 0.80. Model performance varied for any given method between sites and between contaminants (max difference between sites or within contaminants = 0.10). Average sensitivity when the specificity was above 0.70 was 80.6%. Average sensitivity for models predicting arsenic (86.3%) was somewhat better than for uranium (78.4%) or nitrate (77.1%).

If an agency wishes to conduct their own assessment of the risk of elevated groundwater concentrations of specific contaminants, we recommend IDW as it can be implemented using GIS software that is commonly used by environmental health agencies, and is easy to explain to a range of audiences. Improvement in predictive power over the National Screening Model will likely depend on the availability of new sources of spatially-referenced groundwater quality data. Generating site-specific models using readily available data, such as the data we used, may produce also better LUR or CART models for predicting level in that area as long as there are sufficient data. However LUR and CART require specialized software and personnel skilled in statistical analysis.

The data, tools and products developed by this project can facilitate further improvements in predictive models. More accurate site-specific models can be developed where there are additional groundwater data from local sources. Further work should be conducted to assess the effectiveness of the National Screening Model maps in communicating information about risk and uncertainty to practitioners and the general public. As the value of this project lies in the use of the methods and maps, information needs to be disseminated through public health and groundwater organizations. Finally, the impact of such predictive models and maps on public health response and private well owner behaviors, both testing and point-of-use treatment, would provide useful information for increasing the impact of similar research efforts.

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Appendix A: Description of data sources

1. **National Water Information System (NWIS) data:** acquired from National Water Quality Monitoring Council, (<http://www.waterqualitydata.us/>).

Our primary source of data is the NWIS database of water information data compiled by the USGS. A set of 112 relevant water quality parameters were identified. Groundwater data for these 112 parameter codes were downloaded for the contiguous US via the Water Quality Portal (WQP). Well characteristics and geographic coordinates for all water wells (n=273,643) were also downloaded and geolocated using ArcGIS. Data were restructured from 'long' format (one observation per result) to 'wide' format (one observation per sample) using SAS 9.4. Data that measured the same constituent were combined into a single field. Values were converted where needed to reconcile differences in units. Non-detect values were assigned one-half the reported censoring limit. There were too few censored values for any given well to use alternative estimation methods to impute values for the censored observations. Negative values as well as extreme values (based on manual inspection of the upper tail of the distribution) were changed to missing values. The final value, original value (unchanged), non-detect flag, units and original parameter code for each constituent were written into separate fields.

Overall we captured 78,254 valid dissolved arsenic observations, 112,992 valid nitrate observations, and 27,420 valid dissolved uranium observations. Data for other radionuclides (including total alpha activity), and constituents related to groundwater conditions (Cl, Fe, SO₂, SO₄, alkalinity, and conductivity) are also included in the data warehouse. Five hundred meter buffers were generated around the NWIS wells in order to capture the environmental variability around the well and not simply at the well point.

2. **CropScape data layer:** acquired from The USDA-National Agricultural Statistics Service, (<http://nassgeodata.gmu.edu/CropScape/>)

Cropscape raster images categorize land cover based on land use and type. Cropscape rasters were downloaded by state for the contiguous US for all years between 2008 and 2013, resulting in 294 statewide rasters. Cropscape rasters have a resolution of 30m and provide the acreage for 105 specific crops and 21 non-agriculture, land use types. Non-agriculture, land use types were categorized into five categories, including developed, forest/shrublands, wetlands, non-agriculture, and barren. Crops were categorized based on nitrogen fertilizer needs (high-, medium-, and low-N fertilizer use) and crop type (please see Table 1 below). Crop type categories included grains and seeds (high-, med-, and low-N use), stone/miscellaneous fruits (high-, med-, and low-N use), other fruit-berries (low-N use), nuts (high-N use), legumes (med- and low-N use), truck crops (high- and medium-N use), and pasture (high-N use). These 13 agricultural and 5 non-agricultural categories were then used to reclassify each state's cropscape rasters. To improve processing speed, the raster datasets were further simplified

after the reclassification by using the InList tool to remove areas of no concern, e.g., barren land and perennial ice/snow were reclassified as “no data.”

Once the rasters were reclassified they were converted to polygons in order to determine the area of each crop category within the 500 m well buffers and PWUAs using the ‘Tabulate Intersect’ tool. In order to capture crop variation by year for wells and PWUAs, the entire reclassification and tabulate intersect process was repeated for all states in the contiguous US for three years (2008, 2010, and 2012). The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

- 3. Nitrogen fertilizer requirements:** acquired from The University of Wisconsin Extension Service, (<http://learningstore.uwex.edu/assets/pdfs/A2809.pdf>) and (<http://learningstore.uwex.edu/assets/pdfs/A2809.pdf>); and Mississippi State University’s Extension, (<http://msucares.com/pubs/publications/p2647.pdf>).

Fertilization requirements were obtained from several sources, depending on crop type and location of production. Nitrogen application rates were determined by analyzing fertilizer recommendations for various crops. Extension services provide a range of nitrogen needs so it was useful to crosscheck references in order to get a more accurate N range. A nitrogen fertilizer range was assigned to each crop type based on fertilizing needs by season, farming practices, and age of planting. A classification scheme was used for high (100+), med (50-100), and low (0-50) categories. The final categories used in the cropscape layers are provided in Table A1.

Table A1. Crops categories based on nitrogen fertilizer needs (high-, medium-, and low-N fertilizer use) and crop type.

Reclass Code	Reclass Categories
999	No Data
900	Barren
875	Grains & Seeds high-N
850	Grains & Seeds med-N
825	Grains & Seeds low-N
775	Stone/other fruits high N
750	Stone/other fruits med-N
725	Stone fruits/misc. crops low-N
710	Other Fruit (berries)
700	Nuts
650	Legumes med-N
625	Legumes low-N
600	Water, Non-Ag,ice/snow
550	Truck Crops / other high N crops
525	Truck Crops / other med N crops
450	Developed
400	Forest/Shrublands
350	Pasture
300	Wetlands

4. National Land Cover Dataset (NLCD): acquired from the Multi-Resolution Land Characteristics (MRLC) Consortium, (<http://www.mrlc.gov/finddata.php>)

NLCD is a 21-class land cover classification scheme at a spatial resolution of 30m, and is based on the unsupervised classification of Landsat Thematic Mapper imagery. NLCD coverages were downloaded for 1992, 2001, 2006, and 2011. National land cover types include open water, perennial ice/snow, various developed categories, barren land, various forest categories, various scrub categories, various herbaceous categories, various wetland categories, moss and lichen (for AK only), pasture/hay, and cultivated crops. For NO₃-N prediction, CropScape coverages are more detailed, however they only go back to the year 2008. Currently, we are processing NLCD coverages for 1992 and 2001 to extend our temporal window. The data was processed much like CropScape with the data being reclassified into more meaningful, simplified classes.

5. Dasymetric Apportioned Population (DAP) Estimates: Populated areas of the conterminous US were delineated using the DAP Model or similar methodology. Areas where private wells are used, or likely to be used in the near future, were delineated to help focus the geographic extent of the analysis, link the water quality results to specific populations, and estimate nitrogen inputs from on-site sanitation systems. Estimates for the population within each 500 m well buffer were calculated using the PWUA model. These estimates served as a proxy for nitrogen inputs from on-site sanitation systems. (See Appendix B for a detailed description of PWUA model). The population within each 500 m buffer was calculated using areal apportionment, which apportions the population of US Census blocks based on the percent area of blocks contained within the well buffer. In order to estimate nitrogen inputs from on-site sanitation systems prior to 2010, census 2000 blocks and relevant demographics were downloaded and are currently being processed.

6. NTN Deposition: acquired from The National Atmospheric Deposition Program, (<http://nadp.sws.uiuc.edu/ntn/>).

The NTN raster dataset is an atmospheric nitrate deposition map with a 2500m resolution, which was derived from an Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) interpolated surface of atmospheric nitrate deposition. Please refer to the lab and field method documentation on the NADP's website (above) for detailed information on how the dataset was created. For the PWUA the 'zonal statistics' (ZS) tool was used which calculates a min/max/mean nitrate deposition statistic for each PWUA. For the well buffers, a custom tool 'zonal statistics with overlap' (ZO) was downloaded from ESRI (<http://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=b859b33c616a47d2b99b5e133942db02>). This tool accounts for overlapping buffers by iterating through the well buffers. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

7. Irrigated Lands from Remote Sensing: acquired from The University of Wisconsin's Center for Sustainability and the Global Environment (SAGE), (<http://www.sage.wisc.edu/mapsdatamodels.html>).

The dataset is a 500m raster of irrigated lands across the US where each pixel is a value between 0-100% irrigated area. The percent of irrigated land was calculated for each 500 m buffer and PWUA. The data set was processed using the ZO tool for the overlapping well buffers and the ZS tool for PWUA. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

8. Hydrologic Landscape Regions (HLR): acquired from the USGS, (<http://water.usgs.gov/GIS/metadata/usgswrd/XML/hlrus.xml>).

The HLR dataset contains information on climate, soil, terrain, and geologic characteristics for each of the 39,833 watersheds across the US. HLR IDs indicate the number of similar watersheds across the US (1-20). A spatial join was used to determine the HLR(s) for each well and PWUA. Thus, each point or PWUA was linked to a particular HLR(s). The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

- 9. Monthly and Annual Precipitation:** acquired from PRISM Climate Group of Oregon State University, (<http://datagateway.nrcs.usda.gov/>.)

The raster datasets consisted of average monthly and annual precipitation from 1981-2010 (NORM81) and have a 1000m resolution. The underlying precipitation model was based on parameter-elevation regressions on independent slopes model (PRISM). NORM81 monthly and annual data was downloaded for each state in the contiguous US. The data was processed using the zonal statistics tool for the PWUA and with the zonal statistics with overlap tool for the well buffers. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing. Recently, annual precipitation datasets, which were not normalized over a 30-year period, were downloaded for each state in the contiguous US for all years between 1990 and 2013. These annual datasets are currently being processed.

- 10. SSURGO:** acquired from the U.S. Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service, (<http://datagateway.nrcs.usda.gov/>).

SSURGO is a geographic database of soil surveys by state. It is the most detailed level of soil information available. Tabular data is linked to the spatial data via map unit ID. The primary variables included in the NO₃-N prediction model were hydrologic group, water table depth, and percent organic. These variables are contained within the muaggatt table. We also included variables from the new Valu1 table. SSURGO data was downloaded as polygon (feature class) data, the tabulate intersect tool was used to determine soil coverages for both PWUA and well buffers. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

- 11. STATSGO:** acquired from the U.S. Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service, (<http://websoilsurvey.sc.egov.usda.gov/App/HomePage.htm>)

STATSGO is a state soil geographic database provided by the NRCS. In comparison to SSURGO, STATSGO is a more generalized soil map of a state. STATSGO map units can have a large number of soil components, which generalizes soil characteristics over a broad area. STATSGO datasets were downloaded state-by-state for the contiguous US, and coverages are at the 1:250,000 scale. Where possible SSURGO data was used to determine hydrologic group, water table depth, and percent organic in well buffers and PWUAs, however in various areas across the US STATSGO data was used instead. Please refer to the following link for the availability of SSURGO

data as of June 4,
2014: <http://websoilsurvey.nrcs.usda.gov/DataAvailability/SoilDataAvailabilityMap.pdf> .

12. USGS National Hydrography: acquired from the USGS, (<http://nhd.usgs.gov/>)

A national hydrography dataset contains information on surface water for the US and is at the 1:24k-scale. The percentage of water area, as well as the type of water body, was calculated for all 500 m well buffers. The dataset was processed using the tabulate intersect tool. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

13. Impervious surface: acquired from the National Land Cover Database (NLCD) 2011 ed., (http://www.mrlc.gov/nlcd11_data.php).

The percent of impervious surface was calculated for each 500 m buffer. Each raster cell (30m resolution) is given an impervious surface value between 0-100 percent. The data was processed using the zonal statistics tool for the PWUA and with the zonal statistics with overlap tool for the well buffers. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

14. Urbanized/Rural Classification: acquired from The US Census Bureau, (<http://www.census.gov/geo/reference/ua/urban-rural-2010.html>).

The national urban/rural classification dataset includes the following variables: urbanized area, urban cluster, urban population, and rural population. The percent of urban and rural area was calculated for each 500 m buffer. The dataset was processed using the tabulate intersect tool. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

15. County-Level Estimates of Fertilizer Use: acquired from the USGS, (http://water.usgs.gov/GIS/metadata/usgswrd/XML/sir2012-5207_county_fertilizer.xml#stdorder); and USDA 2012 Census of Agriculture (http://www.agcensus.usda.gov/Publications/2012/Online_Resources/Ag_Atlas_Maps/Farms/)

The USGS's county-level estimates of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizer for the contiguous US provides data on the amount (in kilograms) of farm and nonfarm fertilizer used for each year between 1987 and 2006. In addition, county-level estimates of fertilizer use were downloaded from the Census of Agriculture for 1997, 2002, 2007, and 2012. The census datasets are in number of acres treated.

16. National Digital Elevation Model (DEM): acquired from the USGS, (<http://ned.usgs.gov/about.html>).

The DEM raster has a 100m resolution and pixel values represent elevation. The slope was extracted using the 'slope extraction' tool in ArcGIS. The ZS tool was used to extract average slope and elevation for each 500m buffer and PWUA. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

- 17. Major Land Resource Areas (MLRAs):** acquired from the USGS, (<http://water.usgs.gov/GIS/metadata/usgswrd/XML/mlra.xml>)

MLRA are sub regions of the land resource regions and comprise smaller homogeneous areas, which are geographic areas characterized by similar patterns of soil, climate, water resources, and land uses. The scale for the MLRA coverages is 1:2,000,000. A spatial join was used to link MLRA(s) to PWUAs and the well point data. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

- 18. Physiographic divisions of the conterminous US:** acquired from the USGS, (<http://water.usgs.gov/GIS/metadata/usgswrd/XML/physio.xml>)

This coverage represents broad-scale subdivisions based on terrain, rock type, and geologic structure and history, and is based on Fenneman and Johnson's (1946) original map. Detailed methods describing the digitization and processing of the original map to its current form can be found at the above website. For this data a simple spatial join was used, by joining the physiographic regions to the PWUA and the well point data. Thus, each point or PWUA will be linked to a particular physiographic region. The tabular results were exported from ArcGIS as a .txt file and then converted to SAS for further processing.

- 19. Temperature:** acquired from the PRISM Climate Group of Oregon State University, (<http://www.prism.oregonstate.edu/>)

The raster datasets consisted of average monthly and annual temperature from 1981-2010 (NORM81) and have a 1000m resolution. The data provides estimates of minimum and maximum temperature as well as dew point.

- 20. Federal Lands:** acquired from the USGS, (<http://www.nationalatlas.gov/mld/fedlanp.html>)

The federal land coverage provides the extent and boundaries of lands owned by the Federal Government, including Bureau of Land Management, Bureau of Reclamation, the US Department of Agriculture Forest Service, the Department of Defense, the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, the National Park Service, the Tennessee Valley Authority, and other agencies. The layer was created at a scale of 1:2,000,000. Detailed information on the layer can be found at the above website.

21. National Uranium Resource Evaluation (NURE) Hydrogeochemical and Stream Sediment Reconnaissance (HSSR) Data: acquired from the USGS, (<http://mrddata.usgs.gov/nure/sediment/>)

The NURE HSSR database contains information on 335,547 water samples collected across the US between 1975 and 1980. Samples are from stream sediment, groundwater, and surface water.

22. Radiometric Survey of the US: acquired from the USGS, (<http://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2005/1413/>)

This data measures the gamma-ray flux produced by the radioactive decay of certain, natural occurring elements: (K-40,U-28, and Th-232) in the top centimeters of rock and soil from years 1975-1983. The data was acquired in raster format at a resolution of 2000m.

23. Watershed Boundary Dataset (WBD): acquired from the USGS's National Hydrology Dataset the WBD provide hydrologic units defining drainage areas of surface water. The data is at the 1;24,000 scale and was acquired for the conterminous US. (http://nhd.usgs.gov/userGuide/Robohelpfiles/NHD_User_Guide/Feature_Catalog/Watershed_Boundary_Dataset/Watershed_Boundary_Dataset.htm)

24. National Water-Quality Assessment Program (NAWQA): acquired nitrogen and phosphorous load estimates for estuaries and lakes in tabular format. Coverage was for North/South Atlantic and Gulf Coast regions. (http://cida.usgs.gov/nawqa_public/apex/f?p=136:1:0)

25. Community Water Systems (CWS): acquired by data mining through various agencies. These CWS were downloaded in spatial format where available (Table A2). Although multiple states had spatial datasets of private wells, corresponding water quality information was lacking.

Table A2. Availability of CWS and private well spatial data

STATE	Website	CWS GIS Layer	Private Well GIS Layer
AL	-	N	N
AR	-	N	N
AZ	http://www.azwater.gov/azdwr/gis/	Y	N
CA	http://cehtp.org/page.jsp?page_key=762	Y	N
CO	-	N	N
CT	-	N	N
DC	-	N	N
DE	-	N	N
FL	FL provided by contact	Y	Y
GA	-	N	N

IA	http://www.igsb.uiowa.edu/nrgislib/	Y - Points	N
	http://www.igsb.uiowa.edu/nrgislib/	N	Y
ID	http://www.idwr.idaho.gov/GeographicInfo/gisdata/gis_data.htm	Y	N
	http://www.idwr.idaho.gov/GeographicInfo/gisdata/gis_data.htm	N	Y
IL	-	N	N
IN	-	N	N
KS	http://www.kansasgis.org/members/index.cfm	Y	N
KY	-	N	N
LA	http://sonris-gis.dnr.state.la.us/gis/dnld/download.html	N	Y
MA	http://www.mass.gov/anf/research-and-tech/it-serv-and-support/application-serv/office-of-geographic-information-massgis/	Y - Points	N
MD	-	N	N
ME	http://www.maine.gov/megis/catalog/	Y	N
MI	-	N	N
MN	http://www.mngeo.state.mn.us/choose/metadata/wells.html	Y	N
MO	-	N	N
MS	http://www.maris.state.ms.us/HTM/DownloadData/Statewide.html	Y	N
MT	http://apps.msl.mt.gov/Geographic_Information/Data/DataList/datalist_Details.aspx?did={CDC1702D-810F-4055-B956-ED78662BA1F5}	Y - Points	N
NC	-	N	N
ND	-	N	N
NE	-	N	N
NH	-	N	N
NJ	-	N	N
NM	http://www.ose.state.nm.us/water_info_data.html	N	Y
NV	-	N	N
	http://www.maris.state.ms.us/HTM/DownloadData/Statewide.html	N	Y
OH	-	N	N
OK	http://www.owrb.ok.gov/maps/pmg/owrbdata_WS.html	Y	N
	http://www.owrb.ok.gov/maps/pmg/owrbdata_WS.html	N	Y
OR	-	N	N
PA	-	N	N
RI	-	N	N
SC	-	N	N
SD	-	N	N
TN	-	N	N
TX	http://www.tceq.state.tx.us/gis/sites.html	Y	Y
UT	University of Utah, Division of PH	Y	N
VA	-	N	N
VT	http://vcgi.vermont.gov/warehouse/search_tools	N	Y
WA	http://ww4.doh.wa.gov/gis/gisdata.htm	Y	N
	http://www.ecy.wa.gov/services/gis/data/data.htm	N	Y

WI	-	N	N
WV	-	N	N
WY	http://wygl.wygisc.org/wygeolib/catalog/main/home.page;jsessionid=0B53F2389D1C6EB4D501D6330E3E1C56	N	N

26. Geologic Datasets: acquired from the USGS, (<http://mrddata.usgs.gov/geology/state/>) as well as numerous state agencies

Digital geologic map layers were downloaded for all states in the contiguous US. These geologic layers represent areas based on lithology, age, province, and unit name. The state-based coverages range in scale from 1:100,000 to 1:1,000,000. The unit name was matched, when possible, to the local geologic aquifer names from the NWIS data.

27. State Geology: acquired state-level geologic data by data mining state websites for spatial data. Not all states had available data and the resolution varied from 1:24,000 to 1:1,000,000. When available, we downloaded the spatial data to assess the quality and usability of the data for project objectives. Spatial datasets downloaded on a state-by-state basis include, but are not limited to, surficial bedrock layers, principal aquifer layers, and local aquifer layers. Not all states had accessible datasets. State findings were tracked in Table A3.

Table A3. Availability of state-level geology datasets.

STATE	State Geology Website	Geology GIS Layer Available
AL	http://www.gsa.state.al.us/gsa/gis_data.aspx	Y
AR	-	N
AZ	http://earth.gis.usu.edu/swgap/geology.html http://www.azgs.az.gov/	Y
CA	http://www.consrv.ca.gov/CGS/Pages/Index.aspx http://portal.gis.ca.gov/geoportal/catalog/main/home.page	N
CO	http://geosurvey.state.co.us/Pages/CGSHome.aspx http://earth.gis.usu.edu/swgap/geology.html http://water.state.co.us/DataMaps/GISandMaps/Pages/GISDownloads.aspx	Y
CT	http://www.ct.gov/deep/cwp/view.asp?a=2698&q=322898&deepNav_GID=1707	Y
DC	-	N
DE	http://www.dgs.udel.edu/data	Y
FL	http://www.dep.state.fl.us/geology/gisdatamaps/state_geo_map.htm	Y
GA	https://data.georgiaspatial.org/login.asp?CookieTest=2	Y
IA	http://www.igsb.uiowa.edu/webapps/nrgislib/	Y
ID	http://www.idwr.idaho.gov/GeographicInfo/GISdata/geology.htm http://www.idwr.idaho.gov/GeographicInfo/gisdata/aquifers.htm	Y
IL	http://www.isgs.illinois.edu/?q=isgs-online-map-series http://www.isgs.illinois.edu/?q=maps/statewide-maps	N

IN	http://www.in.gov/dnr/water/4302.htm	Y
KS	http://www.kgs.ku.edu/General/Geology/state23.html https://catalog.data.gov/organization/azgs-az-gov?q=kansas&sort=none http://www.kansasgis.org/index.cfm http://www.kansasgis.org/catalog/index.cfm	Y
KY	http://kgs.uky.edu/kgsweb/main.asp	Y
LA	http://sonris-www.dnr.state.la.us/gis/agsweb/IE/JSViewer/index.html?TemplateID=181	Y
MA	http://www.mass.gov/anf/research-and-tech/it-serv-and-support/application-serv/office-of-geographic-information-massgis/online-mapping/ http://www.geo.umass.edu/stategeologist/frame_maps.htm http://www.mass.gov/anf/research-and-tech/it-serv-and-support/application-serv/office-of-geographic-information-massgis/datalayers/sg24k.html	Y
MD	http://www.mgs.md.gov/publications/maps.html	N
ME	http://www.maine.gov/megis/catalog/	Y
MI	http://www.mcgi.state.mi.us/mgdl/?rel=ext&action=sext	Y
MN	http://mcc.mn.gov/gis.html#bedrock_geology_head http://www.dnr.state.mn.us/groundwater/groundwatermgmt.html	Y
MO	http://www.dnr.mo.gov/gis/ http://msdisweb.missouri.edu/geoportal/catalog/main/home.page	Y
MS	http://www.deq.state.ms.us/MDEQ.nsf/page/Geology_surface?OpenDocument	Y
MT	http://www.mbmgs.mtech.edu/gmr/gmr-statemap.asp	Y
NC	http://data.nconemap.com/geoportal/catalog/main/home.page http://www.geology.enr.state.nc.us/maps/GeologicMaps/500k_1985_Geo_Map.html	?
ND	https://www.dmr.nd.gov/ndgs/	Y
NE	http://snr.unl.edu/csd/surveyareas/geology.asp	Y
NH	http://www2.des.state.nh.us/gis/onestop/ http://www.granit.unh.edu/data/downloadfreedata/category/databycategory.html	Y
NJ	https://nigin.state.nj.us/NJ_NJGINExplorer/DataDownloads.jsp http://www.state.nj.us/dep/njgs/geodata/dgs98-5.htm http://www.state.nj.us/dep/njgs/geodata/dgs07-2.htm	Y
NM	http://geoinfo.nmt.edu/publications/maps/geologic/state/home.cfm http://earth.gis.usu.edu/swgap/geology.html	Y
NV	http://www.nbmgs.unr.edu/index.html http://earth.gis.usu.edu/swgap/geology.html	Y
NY	https://www.nysm.nysed.gov/gis/ http://www.dec.ny.gov/lands/36118.html https://gis.ny.gov/gisdata/inventories/details.cfm?DSID=309 http://www.epa.gov/region02/gis/data.htm#ssa	Y
OH	http://geosurvey.ohiodnr.gov/publications-maps-data/digital-map-series	N
OK	http://www.ogs.ou.edu/homepage.php	N
OR	http://www.oregon.gov/DAS/CIO/GEO/pages/alphalist.aspx	Y
PA	http://www.dcnr.state.pa.us/topogeo/publications/digitaldata/index.htm	Y
RI	http://www.edc.uri.edu/rigis/data/	Y
SC	http://www.gis.sc.gov/data.html#GS	Y
SD	http://arcgis.sd.gov/server/sdGIS/Data.aspx	Y
TN	http://tnmap.tn.gov/DataSales.asp	Y
TX	http://www.tnris.org/get-data?quicktabs_maps_data=1	Y

UT	http://geology.utah.gov/maps/gis/ http://earth.gis.usu.edu/swgap/geology.html	Y
VA	http://geog-grant.radford.edu/GIS%20Center/DataDownloader/index.html	Y
VT	http://vcgi.vermont.gov/	Y
WA	http://fortress.wa.gov/dnr/app1/dataweb/dmmatrix.html	Y
WI	http://dnr.wi.gov/maps/gis/	Y
WV	http://wvgis.wvu.edu/data/data.php	N
WY	http://wygl.wygisc.org/wygeolib/catalog/main/home.page	Y

Appendix B: Study site descriptions

Study Site 1: Intermontane Plateau, Columbia Plateau, Payette & Snake River Plains

Contaminants: Arsenic

Figure B1. Distribution of wells in study site 1.

Located west and south of the Rocky Mountain system, the Columbia Plateau portion is characterized by a substratum of nearly horizontal lava flows. The Payette Section (consisting primarily of lacustrine sediments) is west of the Snake River Plain (consisting of relatively young lava plains) (Fenneman and Johnson, 1946). The following states are part of this study site: ID, NV, OR, UT, WY

Area: 44,913 mi²

Population: 423,562

Physiographic divisions: 20c & 20d

Hydrologic Basins: Upper Snake, Middle Snake-Boise, Middle Snake-Powder

Table B1. Average annual precipitation, temperature and PET for study site 1.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Mean annual precipitation (in)	9.5	22.7	-
Mean annual temperature (F°)	37.1	51.1	-
Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (in)	17.7	28.1	-
Slope in % rise	0.006	16.5	4.0

Study Site 2: Atlantic Coastal Plain, Embayed

Contaminants: Nitrate

Figure B2. Distribution of wells in study site 2.

Found along the eastern seaboard of the U.S., it is characterized by land that is cut off from the mainland by sounds and deeply indented estuaries (Fenneman and Johnson, 1946). The following states are part of this study site: DC, DE, MA, MD, NC, NJ, NY, PA, VA

Area: 31,520 mi²

Population: 2,709,003

Physiographic divisions: 3a

Hydrologic basins: Onslow Bay, Upper Chesapeake, James, Potomac, Lower Chesapeake, Pamlico, Neuse, Roanoke, Albemarle-Chowan, Lower Hudson, Upper Delaware, Long Island, Massachusetts-Rhode Island Coastal, Lower Delaware, Mid Atlantic Coastal

Table B2. Average annual precipitation, temperature and PET for study site 2.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Mean annual precipitation (in)	50.0	53.7	-
Mean annual temperature (F°)	49.4	62.0	-
Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (in)	25.4	35.8	-
Slope in % rise	0.004	1.6	0.30

Study Site 3: Interior Plains, Central Lowlands, Osage Plains

Contaminants: Arsenic, Uranium

Figure B3. Distribution of wells in study site 3.

This study site is situated in the relatively low lying areas of the eastern portion of the interior plains. The Osage Plains are the section of the Central Lowlands which lie south of the glaciated area of the region (Fenneman and Johnson, 1946). The following states are part of this study site: KS, MO, OK, TX

Area: 111,833 mi²

Population: 3,038,238

Physiographic divisions: 12f

Hydrologic basins: Osage, Lower Missouri-Blackwater, Kansas, Middle Arkansas, Smoky Hill, Lower Cimarron, Lower Canadian, Lower North Canadian, Robert S. Kerr Reservoir, Washita, Neosho, Arkansas-Keystone, Verdigris, Salt Fork Red, North Fork Red, Lower Beaver,

Upper Trinity, Brazos Headwaters, Upper Colorado, Prairie Dog Town Fork Red, Red-Pease, Red-Lake Texoma

Table B3. Average annual precipitation, temperature and PET for study site 3

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Mean annual precipitation (in)	19.7	43.6	-
Mean annual temperature (F°)	53.1	64.9	-
Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (in)	31.0	40.4	-
Slope in % rise	.01	2.6	0.75

Study Site 4: Interior Plains, Great Plains, High Plains & Colorado Piedmont

Contaminants: Uranium, Nitrate

Figure B4. Distribution of wells in study site 4.

The High Plains are a north-south running belt within the Great Plains, characterized by remnants of sedimentation. The Colorado Piedmont makes up the western portion of the Great Plains (Fenneman and Johnson, 1946). The following states are part of this study site: CO, KS, MO, NE, NM, OK, SD, TX, WY

Area: 179,723 mi²

Population: 1,688,767

Physiographic divisions: 13d & 13f

Hydrologic basins: Upper Arkansas, Republican, South Platte, North Platte, Middle Arkansas, Smoky Hill, Niobrara, Middle Platte, Loup, Elkhorn, Upper Cimarron, Salt Fork Red, North Fork Red, Lower Beaver, Brazos Headwaters, Upper Colorado, Middle Canadian, Prairie Dog Town Fork Red, Upper Beaver

Table B4. Average annual precipitation, temperature and PET for study site 4

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Mean annual precipitation (in)	11.5	29.0	-
Mean annual temperature (F°)	41.9	64.7	-
Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (in)	19.5	39.4	-
Slope in % rise	0.13	12.1	1.04

Study Site 5: California Central Valley

Contaminants: Uranium

Figure B5. Distribution of wells in study site 5.

Situated inland from the Pacific Ocean is the Central Valley of California. The Central Valley is a low alluvial surface consisting primarily of eroded material from the rising Sierra Nevada and Coastal Ranges to the east and west (USGS). The study site is entirely contained within the state of California.

Area: 19,366 mi²

Population: 1,620,781

Physiographic divisions: 24e

Hydrologic basins: Lower Sacramento, Tulare-Buena Vista Lakes, San Joaquin, San Francisco Bay

Table B5. Average annual precipitation, temperature and PET for study site 5.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Mean annual precipitation (in)	29.2	35.0	-
Mean annual temperature (F°)	39.3	47.8	-
Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (in)	20.9	26.5	-
Slope in % rise	.001	3.3	0.88

Study Site 6: Wisconsin

Contaminants: Arsenic, Nitrate

Figure B6. Distribution of wells in study site 6.

The final study site is of the State of Wisconsin, located in the upper-mid-western United States. Wisconsin is made up of three physiographic regions. The northern region of the state is comprised of The Superior Uplands making up the margin of the Laurentian Uplands of Lake Superior. The eastern portion of the state is classified as the Eastern Lake Section of the Interior Plains, defined as areas of broad cuestas and their corresponding lowlands, which are characterized by morainic lakes amongst younger glacial drift. The western region of the state is a part of the Wisconsin Driftless Section consisting of unglaciated areas and eroded drift (Fenneman and Johnson, 1946).

Area: 56,087 mi²

Population: 2,463,200

Hydrologic basins: Lake Superior, Upper Mississippi, Rock, Fox, Upper Illinois, Lake Michigan, Chippewa, Wisconsin, St. Croix

Table B6. Average annual precipitation, temperature and PET for study site 6.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Mean annual precipitation (in)	29.2	35.0	-
Mean annual temperature (F°)	39.3	47.8	-
Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (in)	20.9	26.5	-
Slope in % rise	.001	3.3	0.88

Appendix C: Summary statistics for all As, U, and NO₃-N explanatory variables

Table C1. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, As groundwater concentrations, Site 1

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
As_diss	Arsenic, Dissolved (µg/l)	6177	0	8.03	29.920	0.05	1.00	2.00	3.00	7.00	18.00	950.00
AsGT5	As > 5 µg/l	6177	0	0.33	0.471	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
AsGT10	As > 10 µg/l	6177	0	0.19	0.394	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
Alk_tot	Alkalinity (ueq/L)	5662	515	183.60	95.138	0.20	74.60	121.00	177.00	238.50	304.00	890.00
Cl_diss	Chloride, Dissolved (mg/l)	5598	579	28.03	43.106	0.04	3.46	7.42	15.00	33.90	57.90	850.00
Fe_diss	Iron, Dissolved (µg/l)	5637	540	69.85	421.397	1.50	1.50	3.00	5.00	10.30	88.00	16000.00
Mn_diss	Manganese, Dissolved (µg/l)	5743	434	39.65	219.823	0.05	0.20	0.45	0.50	2.00	78.20	7700.00
conduct_tot	Conductance (ueq/L)	5906	271	583.61	383.123	48.00	230.00	344.00	523.00	715.00	961.00	5730.00
SO4_diss	SO4, Dissolved (mg/L)	5486	691	63.43	104.539	0.05	6.99	18.00	39.50	72.00	124.00	2150.00
NH3_diss	NH3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	5399	778	0.14	0.712	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.06	13.82
NO3_diss	NO3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	5340	837	3.19	5.240	0.01	0.07	0.68	1.73	3.95	7.11	110.00
NO2_diss	NO2, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	5339	838	0.01	0.019	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.77
pH_tot	pH, Total	5934	243	7.59	0.420	4.20	7.10	7.40	7.60	7.80	8.00	10.60
PO4_diss	Phosphate, Dissolved (mg/l as P)	5347	830	0.05	0.084	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.10	4.04
U_diss	Uranium, Dissolved (µg/l)	446	5731	2.51	7.600	0.12	1.23	1.55	1.95	2.35	3.00	157.00
WellDepth	Well Depth (ft)	6170	7	225.92	141.523	26.00	68.00	100.00	200.00	321.80	440.00	596.00
year	Year	6177	0	1995.30	10.715	1970.00	1977.00	1990.00	2000.00	2002.00	2004.00	2013.00
month	Month	6177	0	7.74	1.469	1.00	6.00	7.00	8.00	9.00	10.00	12.00
slope_HLR	Slope (% rise)	6177	0	1.64	1.673	0.00	0.06	0.83	1.33	1.87	3.24	12.66
TAVE	Mean annual temperature (F)	6177	0	47.10	3.333	37.36	42.23	44.78	47.71	50.29	50.56	51.05
PPT	Mean annual precipitation (inches/year)	6177	0	12.44	2.194	10.23	10.69	11.05	11.53	12.89	15.68	22.70

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
PET	Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	6177	0	24.62	2.479	17.95	21.33	22.69	24.61	27.10	27.34	28.10
SAND	Sand in soil (%)	6177	0	33.19	8.947	10.67	22.87	27.22	31.61	38.55	45.18	68.67
PMPE	Mean annual precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	6177	0	-12.19	3.690	-17.40	-16.43	-14.44	-12.37	-10.72	-8.45	4.76
PFLATTOT	Total percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed	6177	0	59.58	25.935	0.00	19.00	41.00	64.00	74.00	96.00	100.00
aqpermnew2	Aquifer permeability class (1-7, lowest-highest)	6177	0	5.23	0.720	2.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
pstream	Proportion of well buffer that is stream	5913	264	0.45	2.955	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	37.88
plake	Proportion of well buffer that is lake	5913	264	0.35	2.881	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	51.67
ilake	Proportion of well buffer that is intermittent lake	5913	264	0.10	1.243	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	26.91
drclass	Drainage Class	6145	32	91.76	21.807	0.00	71.12	99.92	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
flodfrq	Annual probability of flooding	6160	17	0.57	3.667	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	97.97

Table C2. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, As groundwater concentrations, Site 3

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
As_diss	Arsenic, Dissolved (µg/l)	10967	0	3.06	10.52	0.05	0.25	0.25	0.70	2.60	8.00	661.20
AsGT5	As > 5 µg/l	10967	0	0.15	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
AsGT10	As > 10 µg/l	10967	0	0.08	0.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
Alk_tot	Alkalinity (ueq/L)	8222	2745	278.58	142.11	0.50	110.00	190.00	274.00	350.00	432.00	4030.00
Cl_diss	Chloride, Dissolved (mg/l)	7347	3620	156.51	535.26	1.00	5.50	16.00	43.30	130.00	356.00	32860.00
Fe_diss	Iron, Dissolved (µg/l)	10144	823	599.22	4318.47	0.10	5.00	5.00	5.00	23.00	560.00	80000.00
Mn_diss	Manganese, Dissolved (µg/l)	10220	747	164.96	891.83	0.07	1.00	1.00	5.00	90.00	416.50	70000.00
conduct_tot	Conductance (ueq/L)	8314	2653	1706.03	1751.29	10.00	460.00	660.00	1020.00	2200.00	3760.00	22175.00
SO4_diss	SO4, Dissolved (mg/L)	10664	303	312.01	591.07	2.50	10.00	22.00	65.00	235.00	1225.00	11619.00
NH3_diss	NH3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	3013	7954	0.23	1.72	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.08	0.19	0.28	76.07
NO3_diss	NO3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	3034	7933	2.11	5.34	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.09	1.39	7.26	85.00
NO2_diss	NO2, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	1344	9623	0.03	0.23	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	6.76
pH_tot	pH, Total	8290	2677	7.18	0.68	0.70	6.50	6.90	7.10	7.50	7.90	10.60
PO4_diss	Phosphate, Dissolved (mg/l as P)	3015	7952	0.09	0.24	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.13	0.20	10.80
U_diss	Uranium, Dissolved (µg/l)	7235	3732	7.75	23.59	0.01	0.10	0.62	2.56	7.82	18.75	1500.00
WellDepth	Well Depth (ft)	10777	190	107.14	85.57	25.30	33.00	49.00	79.00	131.00	220.00	597.00
year	Year	10967	0	1984.96	10.93	1970.00	1977.00	1978.00	1978.00	1999.00	2002.00	2013.00
month	Month	10967	0	7.43	3.21	1.00	3.00	5.00	8.00	10.00	11.00	12.00
slope_HLR	Slope (% rise)	10967	0	0.61	0.32	0.14	0.20	0.27	0.63	0.83	1.04	2.61
TAVE	Mean annual temperature (F)	10967	0	58.95	2.87	53.33	55.49	55.80	59.59	61.31	62.48	64.75
PPT	Mean annual precipitation (inches/year)	10967	0	31.85	4.94	20.05	24.48	30.13	31.49	34.99	38.03	43.34
PET	Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	10967	0	35.45	2.27	31.26	32.86	33.04	35.96	37.17	38.31	40.33
SAND	Sand in soil (%)	10967	0	27.55	11.23	6.41	11.72	19.47	26.13	35.27	42.85	68.02
PMPE	Mean annual precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	10967	0	-3.60	5.80	-17.23	-13.03	-6.99	-2.58	-0.66	2.41	11.69

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
PFLATTOT	Total percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed	10967	0	80.40	19.41	17.00	51.00	66.00	85.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
aqpermnew2	Aquifer permeability class (1-7, lowest-highest)	10967	0	3.04	2.16	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	6.00	6.00	7.00
pstream	Proportion of well buffer that is stream	4172	6795	0.20	2.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	49.62
plake	Proportion of well buffer that is lake	4172	6795	0.35	2.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	49.56
ilake	Proportion of well buffer that is intermittent lake	4172	6795	0.06	1.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	95.54
drclass	Drainage Class	10897	70	91.49	20.11	0.00	62.35	97.45	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
flodfrq	Annual probability of flooding	10788	179	1.17	5.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.21	100.00

Table C3. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, As groundwater concentrations, Site 6

VAR	_NOBS_	_NMISS_	_MEAN_	_STD_	_MIN_	_P10_	_Q1_	_MEDIAN_	_Q3_	_P90_	_MAX_
As_diss	4937	0	6.13	15.859	0.50	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	636.00
AsGT5	4937	0	0.12	0.322	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
AsGT10	4937	0	0.03	0.178	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
Alk_tot	4359	578	131.99	73.034	2.00	56.00	84.00	121.00	162.00	224.50	656.00
Cl_diss	4357	580	20.63	42.904	0.25	1.50	3.00	9.00	22.00	47.00	889.00
Fe_diss	4786	151	0.45	2.478	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.16	0.93	86.30
Mn_diss	4787	150	0.05	0.176	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.10	4.08
conduct_tot	4357	580	436.14	303.795	10.00	170.00	238.50	366.50	556.00	777.00	5620.00
SO4_diss	4672	265	32.34	89.791	0.10	2.70	8.10	14.70	28.80	63.00	2445.00
NO3_diss	4379	558	2.87	4.498	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.90	4.00	8.40	51.40
pH_tot	4358	579	7.88	0.476	3.31	7.50	7.73	7.94	8.12	8.27	9.91
year	4937	0	2004.28	4.658	1992.00	2000.00	2001.00	2003.00	2006.00	2013.00	2014.00
month	4937	0	6.37	3.059	1.00	2.00	4.00	6.00	9.00	10.00	12.00
slope_HLR	5	4932	0.72	0.016	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.75	0.75
TAVE	5	4932	43.82	0.131	43.75	43.75	43.77	43.77	43.77	44.06	44.06
PPT	5	4932	30.50	0.064	30.38	30.38	30.51	30.53	30.53	30.53	30.53
PET	5	4932	23.40	0.076	23.36	23.36	23.36	23.36	23.38	23.54	23.54
SAND	5	4932	34.48	6.327	30.51	30.51	32.06	32.06	32.06	45.74	45.74
PMPE	5	4932	7.09	0.139	6.85	6.85	7.12	7.17	7.17	7.17	7.17
PFLATTOT	5	4932	75.60	2.608	71.00	71.00	76.00	77.00	77.00	77.00	77.00

VAR	_NOBS_	_NMISS_	_MEAN_	_STD_	_MIN_	_P10_	_Q1_	_MEDIAN_	_Q3_	_P90_	_MAX_
aqpermnew2	5	4932	7.00	0.000	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00
sand2	5	4932	42.00	4.472	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	50.00	50.00
pmpe2	5	4932	10.00	0.000	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
pet2	5	4932	30.00	0.000	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00
ppt2	5	4932	40.00	0.000	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00
pstream	9	4928	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
plake	9	4928	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
ilake	9	4928	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
drclass	9	4928	70.19	20.467	43.60	43.60	47.75	71.60	84.71	99.85	99.85
flodfrq	9	4928	8.56	8.847	0.00	0.00	0.14	10.17	14.22	22.80	22.80
traingrp1	4937	0	0.67	0.471	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table C4. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, U groundwater concentrations, Site 3

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
U_diss	Uranium, Dissolved (µg/l)	7809	0	7.33	22.84	0.01	0.10	0.48	2.24	7.20	17.92	1500.00
UGT15	Uranium > 15 µg/l	7809	0	0.12	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
UGT30	Uranium > 30 µg/l	7809	0	0.05	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
As_diss	Arsenic, Dissolved (µg/l)	7235	574	1.75	10.61	0.06	0.25	0.25	0.50	1.30	3.00	661.20
Alk_tot	Alkalinity (ueq/L)	7619	190	265.20	154.80	0.10	70.00	174.00	267.00	348.00	430.00	4030.00
Cl_diss	Chloride, Dissolved (mg/l)	4807	3002	229.61	2867.48	0.67	5.00	16.00	45.00	160.00	446.00	194000.00
Fe_diss	Iron, Dissolved (µg/l)	7218	591	65.09	1567.74	1.50	5.00	5.00	5.00	13.00	24.00	80000.00
Mn_diss	Manganese, Dissolved (µg/l)	7369	440	68.60	914.46	0.07	1.00	1.00	2.00	10.00	68.00	70000.00
conduct_tot	Conductance (ueq/L)	7687	122	1662.08	2839.44	10.00	440.00	640.00	990.00	2040.00	3550.00	200000.00
SO4_diss	SO4, Dissolved (mg/L)	7142	667	344.95	622.51	1.11	8.00	20.00	66.00	292.00	1312.00	11619.00
NH3_diss	NH3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	313	7496	0.10	0.27	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.24	2.17
NO3_diss	NO3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	313	7496	3.05	7.89	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.56	2.60	8.30	85.00
NO2_diss	NO2, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	312	7497	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.26
pH_tot	pH, Total	7677	132	7.19	0.66	0.70	6.60	6.90	7.20	7.50	7.90	10.60
PO4_diss	Phosphate, Dissolved (mg/l as P)	313	7496	0.04	0.13	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.07	2.19
WellDepth	Well Depth (ft)	7772	37	101.34	85.84	25.30	33.00	46.00	75.00	121.00	200.00	597.00
year	Year	7809	0	1979.07	4.99	1971.00	1978.00	1978.00	1978.00	1978.00	1979.00	2013.00
month	Month	7809	0	7.47	2.99	1.00	3.00	6.00	8.00	10.00	11.00	12.00
slope_HLR	Slope (% rise)	7809	0	0.73	0.26	0.01	0.41	0.56	0.72	0.88	1.07	2.61
TAVE	Mean annual temperature (F)	7809	0	60.01	2.49	53.33	56.03	58.55	60.55	61.64	63.01	64.71
PPT	Mean annual precipitation (inches/year)	7809	0	32.64	5.68	20.05	24.08	28.33	33.25	36.78	40.27	43.59
PET	Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	7809	0	36.23	2.05	31.33	32.94	35.09	36.63	37.59	38.82	40.33
SAND	Sand in soil (%)	7809	0	26.42	11.57	6.51	10.89	16.89	25.52	34.50	42.60	68.02
PMPE	Mean annual precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	7809	0	-3.59	6.61	-17.23	-13.54	-9.02	-2.81	0.89	4.91	11.69

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
PFLATTOT	Total percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed	7809	0	74.72	18.01	17.00	48.00	62.00	76.00	90.00	98.00	100.00
aqpermnew2	Aquifer permeability class (1-7, lowest-highest)	7809	0	2.07	1.57	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	5.00	7.00
pstream	Proportion of well buffer that is stream	867	6942	0.10	1.47	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.60
plake	Proportion of well buffer that is lake	867	6942	0.49	2.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	27.62
ilake	Proportion of well buffer that is intermittent lake	867	6942	0.03	0.98	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.84
drclass	Drainage Class	7794	15	96.34	16.80	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
flodfrq	Annual probability of flooding	7645	164	0.74	5.41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00

Table C5. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, U groundwater concentrations, Site 4

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
U_diss	Uranium, Dissolved (µg/l)	5960	0	20.58	194.11	0.01	0.80	2.94	6.10	11.90	27.44	5720.00
UGT15	Uranium > 15 µg/l	5960	0	0.20	0.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
UGT30	Uranium > 30 µg/l	5960	0	0.09	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
As_diss	Arsenic, Dissolved (µg/l)	5615	345	3.56	5.24	0.06	0.50	1.10	2.30	4.60	7.30	170.00
Alk_tot	Alkalinity (ueq/L)	5327	633	220.75	88.23	0.50	132.00	165.00	210.00	267.00	320.00	1042.00
Cl_diss	Chloride, Dissolved (mg/l)	5530	430	50.16	219.64	0.25	5.00	5.00	12.00	29.00	93.50	6800.00
Fe_diss	Iron, Dissolved (µg/l)	5645	315	89.37	1263.75	1.50	5.00	5.00	5.00	8.00	25.00	80000.00
Mn_diss	Manganese, Dissolved (µg/l)	5812	148	124.23	699.73	0.05	1.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	47.40	14500.00
conduct_tot	Conductance (ueq/L)	5614	346	998.34	1315.63	20.00	280.00	408.00	590.00	910.00	2300.00	18700.00
SO4_diss	SO4, Dissolved (mg/L)	5870	90	250.12	689.18	0.05	2.50	10.00	26.00	126.00	686.50	13900.00
NH3_diss	NH3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	932	5028	0.57	4.71	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.08	0.83	100.12
NO3_diss	NO3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	2106	3854	7.13	9.49	0.01	0.37	1.30	3.53	10.00	18.00	107.00
NO2_diss	NO2, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	633	5327	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.43
pH_tot	pH, Total	5845	115	7.35	0.45	3.30	6.80	7.10	7.40	7.60	7.80	9.60
PO4_diss	Phosphate, Dissolved (mg/l as P)	1531	4429	0.30	1.85	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.17	0.29	29.00
WellDepth	Well Depth (ft)	5564	396	201.62	126.37	26.00	56.00	98.00	179.50	289.00	394.00	597.00
year	Year	5960	0	1982.87	9.92	1972.00	1978.00	1978.00	1979.00	1979.00	2002.00	2013.00
month	Month	5960	0	7.16	2.58	1.00	3.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	11.00	12.00
slope_HLR	Slope (% rise)	5960	0	0.92	0.81	0.14	0.31	0.48	0.76	1.14	1.45	8.67
TAVE	Mean annual temperature (F)	5960	0	52.20	4.86	43.23	46.87	48.07	50.18	57.48	59.10	64.70
PPT	Mean annual precipitation (inches/year)	5960	0	19.86	3.76	13.15	15.40	16.92	19.63	22.41	25.67	28.96
PET	Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	5960	0	29.05	3.81	20.81	24.59	25.15	28.66	32.46	34.36	39.45
SAND	Sand in soil (%)	5960	0	33.86	19.78	2.81	7.32	19.61	34.47	45.32	56.12	87.08

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
PMPE	Mean annual precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	5960	0	-9.19	4.24	-25.87	-14.01	-12.87	-9.53	-6.39	-2.42	-0.14
PFLATTOT	Total percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed	5960	0	67.11	26.07	2.00	31.00	47.00	70.00	92.00	99.00	100.00
aqpermnew2	Aquifer permeability class (1-7, lowest-highest)	5960	0	5.29	1.42	1.00	2.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
pstream	Proportion of well buffer that is stream	1239	4721	0.27	1.92	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.95
plake	Proportion of well buffer that is lake	1239	4721	0.23	1.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	19.96
ilake	Proportion of well buffer that is intermittent lake	1239	4721	0.18	1.41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	19.83
drclass	Drainage Class	5947	13	95.80	17.52	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
flodfrq	Annual probability of flooding	5894	66	1.13	8.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00

Table C6. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, U groundwater concentrations, Site 5

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
U_diss	Uranium, Dissolved (µg/l)	1611	0	20.49	94.36	0.01	0.12	0.70	3.14	12.37	45.10	3085.00
UGT15	Uranium > 15 µg/l	1611	0	0.22	0.41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
UGT30	Uranium > 30 µg/l	1611	0	0.14	0.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
As_diss	Arsenic, Dissolved (µg/l)	653	958	8.99	21.34	0.10	0.87	1.50	3.00	6.30	15.30	230.00
Alk_tot	Alkalinity (ueq/L)	1153	458	59.54	170.25	0.20	1.00	1.60	2.50	4.60	225.33	1840.00
Cl_diss	Chloride, Dissolved (mg/l)	1553	58	164.27	983.77	0.76	5.34	8.80	18.20	46.50	141.00	15000.00
Fe_diss	Iron, Dissolved (µg/l)	628	983	559.17	4824.62	1.50	1.60	3.00	5.00	11.00	90.00	80000.00
Mn_diss	Manganese, Dissolved (µg/l)	1218	393	381.35	2501.51	0.05	0.10	0.50	37.00	163.00	489.00	67000.00
conduct_tot	Conductance (ueq/L)	1599	12	1326.70	4647.61	4.00	210.00	325.00	519.00	900.00	1420.00	60000.00
SO4_diss	SO4, Dissolved (mg/L)	618	993	828.08	3528.07	0.05	6.58	14.40	33.95	89.70	696.00	34000.00
NH3_diss	NH3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	536	1075	0.09	0.85	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	18.02
NO3_diss	NO3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	638	973	7.69	11.74	0.01	0.05	1.20	4.41	9.92	18.00	185.00
NO2_diss	NO2, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	640	971	0.02	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.87
pH_tot	pH, Total	1551	60	7.58	0.57	5.50	7.00	7.20	7.50	7.90	8.30	10.20
PO4_diss	Phosphate, Dissolved (mg/l as P)	566	1045	0.16	0.43	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.09	0.27	6.16
WellDepth	Well Depth (ft)	1611	0	196.52	122.78	29.00	68.00	100.00	166.00	250.00	400.00	586.00
year	Year	1611	0	1988.33	10.80	1970.00	1980.00	1980.00	1980.00	2001.00	2003.00	2013.00
month	Month	1611	0	6.53	2.41	1.00	3.00	4.00	8.00	8.00	9.00	12.00
slope_HLR	Slope (% rise)	1608	3	1.18	1.28	0.04	0.13	0.37	0.77	1.30	3.24	13.47
TAVE	Mean annual temperature (F)	1608	3	61.02	0.95	55.88	59.74	60.36	61.14	61.45	62.35	63.37

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
PPT	Mean annual precipitation (inches/year)	1608	3	15.70	5.43	7.76	10.46	11.80	13.91	19.31	21.46	43.00
PET	Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	1608	3	34.51	1.36	30.41	32.79	33.19	34.87	35.29	36.34	37.69
SAND	Sand in soil (%)	1608	3	41.63	10.23	11.47	25.51	36.00	44.82	51.27	51.27	61.66
PMPE	Mean annual precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	1608	3	-18.81	6.45	-29.92	-25.58	-22.82	-21.22	-13.93	-11.41	11.83
PFLATTOT	Total percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed	1608	3	79.59	19.70	2.00	53.00	68.00	89.00	93.00	100.00	100.00
aqpermnew2	Aquifer permeability class (1-7, lowest-highest)	1608	3	5.70	0.61	1.00	5.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
pstream	Proportion of well buffer that is stream	656	955	0.22	2.46	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	47.46
plake	Proportion of well buffer that is lake	656	955	0.09	1.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	29.16
ilake	Proportion of well buffer that is intermittent lake	656	955	0.02	0.32	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.54
drclass	Drainage Class	1556	55	82.77	34.99	0.00	0.00	98.23	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
flodfrq	Annual probability of flooding	1587	24	0.49	3.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	69.10

Table C7. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, NO3-N groundwater concentrations, Site 2

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
NO3_diss	NO3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	3467	0	3.19	17.68	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.83	4.00	8.11	999.00
NO3GT10	NO3-N > 10 mg/l	3467	0	0.07	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
NO3GT5	NO3-N > 5 mg/l	3467	0	0.20	0.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
NH3_diss	NH3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	3193	274	0.23	0.99	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.08	0.54	23.41
NO2_diss	NO2, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	3398	69	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	1.29
Alk_tot	Alkalinity (ueq/L)	1555	1912	70.09	91.23	0.38	2.00	4.80	29.00	109.00	192.00	770.00
As_diss	Arsenic, Dissolved (µg/l)	689	2778	1.22	4.25	0.05	0.06	0.10	0.20	0.50	1.60	42.30
Cl_diss	Chloride, Dissolved (mg/l)	2432	1035	226.30	1803.63	0.04	4.25	7.90	16.00	55.75	153.00	42600.00
Fe_diss	Iron, Dissolved (µg/l)	1766	1701	2057.36	6853.51	1.50	3.20	5.00	24.00	643.00	5700.00	80000.00
Mn_diss	Manganese, Dissolved (µg/l)	1681	1786	193.30	939.33	0.07	1.24	7.08	26.80	79.00	252.00	21800.00
conduct_tot	Conductance (ueq/L)	3237	230	579.30	2841.17	17.00	71.00	110.00	181.00	367.00	864.00	44100.00
SO4_diss	SO4, Dissolved (mg/L)	2314	1153	52.14	255.42	0.05	0.50	3.85	12.55	36.60	71.30	5640.00
U_diss	Uranium, Dissolved (µg/l)	418	3049	0.11	0.63	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.18	9.97
pH_tot	pH, Total	3177	290	6.05	0.98	3.60	4.80	5.40	6.00	6.70	7.30	11.10
PO4_diss	Phosphate, Dissolved (mg/l as P)	2292	1175	0.05	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.10	2.51
year	Year	3467	0	2005.32	3.84	1999.00	2000.00	2002.00	2005.00	2009.00	2010.00	2013.00
month	Month	3467	0	7.46	2.12	1.00	5.00	7.00	8.00	8.00	10.00	12.00
WellDepth	Well Depth (ft)	3429	38	123.89	112.02	25.30	38.00	53.83	82.04	126.00	305.00	575.00
pctN1	% well buffer with no nitrogen application	2676	791	86.63	23.45	1.08	45.19	84.18	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
pctN2	% well buffer with low nitrogen application (0-50 lb/acre)	2676	791	1.17	5.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.20	63.86
pctN3	% well buffer with medium nitrogen application (50-100 lb/acre)	2676	791	1.17	5.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.22	75.69
pctN4	% well buffer with high nitrogen application (100-250 lb/acre)	2676	791	10.86	21.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.96	48.95	91.50
pctNhi	% well buffer with high nitrogen application (50-250 lb/acre)	2676	791	12.02	21.94	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	12.52	50.86	91.74
NTN	Nitrogen deposition (mg/L)	3362	105	10.93	2.49	6.10	8.18	8.82	10.16	12.70	14.65	17.67
POP	Total population in well buffer	3467	0	62.88	317.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	23.94	160.87	7160.91
AQPERMNEW	Aquifer permeability class (1-7, lowest-highest)	3259	208	4.60	1.38	1.21	3.00	3.00	4.70	6.00	6.00	7.00
slope_HLR	Slope (% rise)	3259	208	0.45	0.24	0.01	0.13	0.23	0.48	0.62	0.62	1.47
TAVE	Mean annual temperature (F)	3259	208	52.78	2.76	49.45	49.56	49.56	53.23	54.11	55.91	62.04
PPT	Mean annual precipitation (inches/year)	3259	208	45.33	1.48	41.53	43.25	43.97	45.70	46.31	46.32	53.71
PET	Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	3259	208	28.60	2.43	25.50	25.57	25.57	29.29	30.06	31.17	35.84
SAND	Sand in soil (%)	3259	208	57.11	14.10	24.29	34.89	43.11	60.76	69.71	69.71	83.30
PMPE	Mean annual precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	3259	208	16.72	3.22	10.23	12.64	13.90	16.06	20.74	20.74	20.81
MINELE	Minimum elevation in watershed (m)	3259	208	3.20	4.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	3.00	8.00	30.00

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
RELIEF	Maximum elevation in watershed minus minimum elevation in watershed (m)	3259	208	50.58	23.88	2.00	18.00	30.00	58.00	58.00	72.00	207.00
PFLATTOT	Total percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed	3259	208	87.22	12.32	34.00	79.00	84.00	84.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
PFLATLOW	Percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed lowland (elevation less than midpoint between minimum and maximum elevation)	3259	208	59.46	18.91	4.00	32.00	52.00	62.00	71.00	79.00	99.00
PFLATUP	Percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed upland (elevation greater than or equal to midpoint between minimum and maximum elevation)	3259	208	27.76	22.98	0.00	5.00	12.00	22.00	39.00	67.00	95.00
pstream	Proportion of well buffer that is stream	3467	0	0.39	3.42	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
plake	Proportion of well buffer that is lake	3467	0	0.63	3.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.54	47.80
ilake	Proportion of well buffer that is intermittent lake	3467	0	0.94	5.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	87.54
totwat	Water, Total	3467	0	1.97	7.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.58	100.00
meanslope	Mean slope (%)	2676	791	0.87	0.70	0.00	0.24	0.40	0.61	1.24	1.68	4.65
slope_cat	Mean slope (%), Categories	2676	791	9.99	0.33	0.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
hydrpAB	% soil in buffer with A or B	1892	1575	83.37	22.21	0.00	51.35	77.05	91.47	100.00	100.00	100.00

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
hydgrpAB2	% soil in buffer with A or B, categories	1892	1575	86.59	21.23	0.00	60.00	80.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
drclass	Drainage Class	2088	1379	79.18	26.56	0.00	44.29	70.63	88.22	100.00	100.00	100.00
pond	% area with ponding	2644	823	6.61	14.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.17	5.24	23.37	100.00
slope_SSURGO	Slope (%)	2644	823	3.35	2.73	0.17	1.16	2.01	2.35	4.04	6.12	24.98
flodfrq	Annual probability of flooding	2606	861	3.79	9.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.62	14.31	100.00
pcturb	% urban area	2676	791	0.68	0.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
imperv	% area in buffer that is impervious	2676	791	27.74	26.87	0.00	0.52	3.81	18.49	48.67	72.19	89.79
impervcat	% area in buffer that is impervious, Categories	2676	791	33.25	26.12	0.00	10.00	10.00	20.00	50.00	80.00	90.00
irrig	% area in buffer that is irrigated	2676	791	2.22	7.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.25	68.76
irrigcat	% area in buffer that is irrigated, categories	2676	791	3.02	8.77	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	70.00
precipmon	Monthly Precip (mm)	3467	0	102.11	17.68	56.90	80.21	88.01	103.48	112.37	123.13	270.97
precipyr	Average annual precip (mm)	3467	0	1204.26	153.22	778.35	1007.00	1120.75	1198.81	1284.88	1416.96	2128.27
precipmonlag	Average precip in preceding month (mm)	3467	0	100.82	18.37	53.74	78.13	90.84	100.82	109.62	120.92	220.17
traingrp1	Training Group	3467	0	0.68	0.47	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table C8. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, NO3-N groundwater concentrations, Site 4

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
NO3_diss	NO3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	1848	0	6.58	7.635	0.01	0.50	2.12	5.04	7.93	13.30	106.00
NO3GT10	NO3-N > 10 mg/l	1848	0	0.17	0.374	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
NO3GT5	NO3-N > 5 mg/l	1848	0	0.50	0.500	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
NH3_diss	NH3, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	1779	69	0.06	0.335	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.06	9.49
NO2_diss	NO2, Dissolved (mg/l as N)	1798	50	0.01	0.031	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.51
Alk_tot	Alkalinity (ueq/L)	455	1393	219.32	79.064	20.50	134.00	161.00	214.00	265.00	308.00	577.00
As_diss	Arsenic, Dissolved (µg/l)	528	1320	5.44	6.575	0.06	0.50	1.60	4.40	7.00	10.80	70.30
Cl_diss	Chloride, Dissolved (mg/l)	1149	699	50.40	198.834	0.04	3.62	7.57	17.20	42.20	108.00	4770.00
Fe_diss	Iron, Dissolved (µg/l)	957	891	73.37	826.230	1.50	2.00	3.20	5.00	5.00	22.50	23600.00
Mn_diss	Manganese, Dissolved (µg/l)	1042	806	71.43	294.681	0.05	0.10	0.41	1.00	3.76	123.00	3470.00
conduct_tot	Conductance (ueq/L)	1774	74	869.42	618.710	79.00	365.00	498.00	710.50	1070.00	1390.00	6200.00
SO4_diss	SO4, Dissolved (mg/L)	1074	774	179.88	348.303	0.05	11.20	23.70	57.80	198.00	370.00	3020.00
U_diss	Uranium, Dissolved (µg/l)	544	1304	16.07	43.418	0.01	0.57	3.48	8.56	17.65	37.00	941.00
pH_tot	pH, Total	1805	43	7.34	0.453	5.80	6.90	7.10	7.30	7.60	7.80	11.90
PO4_diss	Phosphate, Dissolved (mg/l as P)	1642	206	0.08	0.247	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.17	5.11
year	Year	1848	0	2004.67	3.876	1999.00	2000.00	2001.00	2004.00	2008.00	2010.00	2013.00
month	Month	1848	0	5.99	2.740	1.00	3.00	3.00	6.00	8.00	10.00	12.00
WellDepth	Well Depth (ft)	1495	353	128.11	106.596	26.00	43.00	57.00	85.00	160.00	280.00	595.00
pctN1	% well buffer with no nitrogen application	1848	0	57.57	35.111	0.00	5.66	23.51	69.65	88.25	100.00	100.00

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
pctN2	% well buffer with low nitrogen application (0-50 lb/acre)	1848	0	1.04	5.645	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	57.87
pctN3	% well buffer with medium nitrogen application (50-100 lb/acre)	1848	0	10.29	20.623	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	12.99	28.48	100.00
pctN4	% well buffer with high nitrogen application (100-250 lb/arce)	1848	0	30.46	35.949	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.66	64.74	91.26	100.00
pctNhi	% well buffer with high nitrogen application (50-250 lb/arce)	1848	0	40.75	34.487	0.00	0.00	11.38	28.48	71.00	93.87	100.00
NTN	Nitrogen deposition (mg/L)	1848	0	4.30	1.474	2.01	2.87	3.19	3.78	5.02	6.88	9.99
POP	Total population in well buffer	1848	0	77.03	149.555	0.00	0.23	1.07	5.62	105.76	218.79	1522.51
AQPERMNEW	Aquifer permeability class (1-7, lowest-highest)	1848	0	3.92	2.196	1.00	1.32	1.32	5.60	6.00	6.00	6.00
slope_HLR	Slope (% rise)	1848	0	1.90	1.499	0.18	0.38	0.71	1.37	4.23	4.23	6.13
TAVE	Mean annual temperature (F)	1848	0	48.37	3.120	44.33	46.09	46.09	47.37	48.79	50.83	64.70
PPT	Mean annual precipitation (inches/year)	1848	0	17.30	3.352	11.86	14.45	15.40	16.13	17.42	22.52	28.56
PET	Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	1848	0	25.39	2.891	21.24	22.83	22.83	24.60	26.75	29.36	39.45
SAND	Sand in soil (%)	1848	0	40.30	15.720	2.89	17.34	36.81	43.88	45.41	57.09	86.79
PMPE	Mean annual precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration (inches/year)	1848	0	-8.08	2.970	-25.87	-10.98	-9.53	-8.10	-6.70	-4.65	-0.83
MINELE	Minimum elevation in watershed (m)	1848	0	1268.78	377.697	396.00	686.00	1055.00	1285.00	1612.00	1612.00	2122.00
RELIEF	Maximum elevation in watershed minus minimum elevation in watershed (m)	1848	0	735.02	801.722	32.00	109.00	168.00	308.00	2045.00	2045.00	2045.00

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
PFLATTOT	Total percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed	1848	0	46.23	31.452	2.00	11.00	11.00	41.00	76.00	98.00	100.00
PFLATLOW	Percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed lowland (elevation less than midpoint between minimum and maximum elevation)	1848	0	28.01	17.464	1.00	11.00	11.00	27.00	40.00	51.00	89.00
PFLATUP	Percent flat land (slope less than 1 percent) in watershed upland (elevation greater than or equal to midpoint between minimum and maximum elevation)	1848	0	18.22	21.088	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.00	34.00	52.00	91.00
pstream	Proportion of well buffer that is stream	1848	0	0.17	1.438	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.70
plake	Proportion of well buffer that is lake	1848	0	0.14	1.340	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	24.90
ilake	Proportion of well buffer that is intermittent lake	1848	0	0.15	1.265	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	19.83
totwat	Water, Total	1848	0	0.46	2.423	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	27.64
meanslope	Mean slope (%)	1848	0	1.03	0.682	0.01	0.28	0.51	0.96	1.32	1.78	6.03
slope_cat	Mean slope (%), Categories	1848	0	10.00	0.000	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
hydgrpAB	% soil in buffer with A or B	1847	1	95.22	11.917	14.41	87.60	96.44	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
hydgrpAB2	% soil in buffer with A or B, categories	1847	1	96.89	10.706	20.00	90.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
drclass	Drainage Class	1848	0	94.72	15.624	0.00	80.34	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
pond	% area with ponding	1848	0	0.61	2.527	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.94	31.39
slope_SSURGO	Slope (%)	1848	0	3.88	3.247	0.00	0.81	2.00	3.16	4.67	8.21	36.34
flodfrq	Annual probability of flooding	1848	0	6.76	13.779	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.23	23.34	69.61

Variable	Variable	# of Observations	# of Missing Observations	Mean	STD	Min	P10	Q1	Median	Q3	P90	Max
pcturb	% urban area	1848	0	0.32	0.434	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.92	1.00	1.00
imperv	% area in buffer that is impervious	1848	0	12.05	15.194	0.00	0.08	0.25	0.91	25.17	37.09	50.67
impervcat	% area in buffer that is impervious, Categories	1848	0	19.20	13.506	0.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	30.00	40.00	60.00
irrig	% area in buffer that is irrigated	1848	0	15.93	22.627	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.65	52.25	80.21
irrigcat	% area in buffer that is irrigated, categories	1848	0	18.26	24.633	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	60.00	90.00
precipmon	Monthly Precip (mm)	1848	0	36.03	20.015	6.34	15.14	18.24	34.26	50.44	62.27	155.93
precipyr	Average annual precip (mm)	1848	0	365.51	122.523	154.63	234.98	280.57	344.69	435.52	512.03	1038.90
precipmonlag	Average precip in preceding month (mm)	1848	0	32.20	23.315	4.30	4.87	5.76	33.15	42.28	63.45	140.39
traingrp1	Training Group	1848	0	0.66	0.474	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table C9. Summary statistics for all explanatory variables, NO3-N groundwater concentrations, Site 6

<u>_VAR_</u>	<u>_NOBS_</u>	<u>_NMISS_</u>	<u>_MEAN_</u>	<u>_STD_</u>	<u>_MIN_</u>	<u>_P10_</u>	<u>_Q1_</u>	<u>_MEDIAN_</u>	<u>_Q3_</u>	<u>_P90_</u>	<u>_MAX_</u>
NO3_diss	16798	0	3.74	5.414	0.05	0.05	0.10	1.50	5.30	10.70	85.00
NO3GT10	16798	0	0.11	0.313	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
NO3GT5	16798	0	0.26	0.440	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Alk_tot	15950	848	177.58	105.466	2.00	44.00	91.50	164.00	263.00	325.00	795.00
As_diss	4303	12495	5.58	11.727	0.50	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	636.00
Cl_diss	16026	772	23.32	55.248	0.25	1.00	3.00	10.00	24.50	53.00	2638.00
Fe_diss	5182	11616	0.40	2.144	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.13	0.77	84.28
Mn_diss	5100	11698	0.04	0.144	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.07	3.82
conduct_tot	15952	846	465.89	313.293	2.00	146.50	252.00	417.00	610.00	822.00	5920.00
SO4_diss	4189	12609	32.75	88.228	0.10	3.40	8.70	15.20	29.70	64.50	2445.00
pH_tot	15953	845	7.79	0.508	3.31	7.18	7.64	7.91	8.10	8.25	10.18
year	16798	0	2003.38	4.019	1999.00	1999.00	2000.00	2003.00	2005.00	2013.00	2013.00
month	16798	0	6.31	2.968	1.00	2.00	4.00	6.00	9.00	10.00	12.00
pctN1	7637	9161	63.66	28.513	0.00	20.83	41.12	67.46	90.08	100.00	100.00
pctN2	7637	9161	1.79	7.089	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.87	72.05
pctN3	7637	9161	2.35	8.028	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.49	85.56
pctN4	7637	9161	32.13	26.961	0.00	0.00	7.78	27.00	52.49	72.31	100.00
pctNhi	7637	9161	34.47	26.912	0.00	0.00	9.61	31.33	55.08	73.50	100.00
NTN	7637	9161	10.70	2.043	5.40	8.13	8.89	10.90	11.98	13.33	16.37
POP	7510	9288	40.68	66.904	0.00	4.57	7.84	14.89	41.88	107.17	713.10

VAR	_NOBS_	_NMISS_	_MEAN_	_STD_	_MIN_	_P10_	_Q1_	_MEDIAN_	_Q3_	_P90_	_MAX_
AQPERMNEW	7630	9168	2.55	1.461	1.00	1.01	1.48	2.00	3.40	4.84	7.00
slope_HLR	7630	9168	0.62	0.361	0.00	0.26	0.38	0.54	0.71	1.08	2.61
TAVE	7630	9168	43.62	1.614	39.38	41.16	42.97	43.80	44.81	45.40	46.88
PPT	7630	9168	31.74	0.664	30.11	30.78	31.25	31.86	32.28	32.45	34.36
PET	7630	9168	24.00	1.134	20.96	22.34	23.53	24.12	24.87	25.32	26.28
SAND	7630	9168	47.70	20.323	3.96	20.36	29.82	50.25	63.69	74.80	87.94
PMPE	7630	9168	7.74	1.440	4.30	5.50	6.60	8.03	8.76	9.66	11.85
MINELE	7630	9168	291.67	68.311	176.00	225.00	236.00	285.00	320.00	387.50	502.00
RELIEF	7630	9168	91.27	41.224	0.00	47.00	64.00	81.00	112.00	148.00	312.00
PFLATTOT	7630	9168	82.62	19.244	16.00	50.00	76.00	91.00	97.00	99.00	100.00
PFLATLOW	7630	9168	53.84	23.366	0.00	22.00	35.00	62.00	71.00	82.00	100.00
PFLATUP	7630	9168	28.79	18.338	0.00	9.00	15.00	25.00	41.00	57.00	85.00
pstream	7637	9161	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
plake	7637	9161	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
ilake	7637	9161	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
totwat	7637	9161	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
meanslope	7637	9161	1.33	1.662	0.00	0.14	0.37	0.87	1.70	2.90	44.87
slope_cat	7637	9161	9.51	2.456	0.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	50.00
hydgrpAB	7637	9161	82.43	22.924	0.00	45.89	72.14	93.27	100.00	100.00	100.00
hydgrpAB2	7637	9161	85.53	21.595	0.00	50.00	80.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
drclass	7435	9363	73.51	27.988	0.00	28.58	58.04	82.70	97.92	100.00	100.00

VAR	_NOBS_	_NMISS_	_MEAN_	_STD_	_MIN_	_P10_	_Q1_	_MEDIAN_	_Q3_	_P90_	_MAX_
pond	7438	9360	14.30	17.951	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.48	23.17	38.66	100.00
slope_SSURGO	7438	9360	5.31	4.199	0.96	1.38	2.32	3.97	7.00	11.16	32.98
flodfrq	7438	9360	3.25	7.334	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.65	11.55	87.71
pcturb	7506	9292	0.07	0.222	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14	1.00
imperv	7637	9161	3.26	5.762	0.00	0.27	0.54	1.15	2.94	8.51	57.52
impervcat	7637	9161	11.19	4.893	0.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	60.00
irrig	7637	9161	1.31	5.525	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	63.03
irrigcat	7637	9161	1.72	6.783	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	70.00
precipmon	7637	9161	75.70	30.338	14.59	27.87	52.16	79.37	98.57	111.53	154.61
precipyr	7637	9161	814.70	101.772	553.47	673.15	731.88	826.24	883.82	935.57	1118.11
precipmonlag	7637	9161	73.78	31.537	15.53	25.83	45.25	78.71	97.00	110.76	151.69
traingrp1	16798	0	0.67	0.469	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Appendix D: Final CART models for As, U, and NO₃-N study sites

FigureD1-A. CART diagram for arsenic model, Study Site 1, Part A

Figure D1-B. CART diagram for final arsenic model, Study Site 1, Part B

Figure D2-A. CART diagram for final arsenic model, Study Site 3, Part A.

Figure D2-B. CART diagram for final As model, Study Site 3, Part B.

Figure D3-A. CART diagram for final As model, Study Site 6, Part A.

Figure D3-B. CART diagram for final As model, Study Site 6, Part B.

Figure D4-A. CART diagram for final U model, Study Site 3, Part A.

Figure D4-B. CART diagram for final U model, Study Site 3, Part B.

Figure D5-A. CART diagram for final U model, Study Site 4, Part A.

Figure D6. CART diagram for final U model, Study Site 5.

Figure D7-A. CART diagram for final nitrate model, Study Site 2, Part A.

Figure D7-B. CART diagram for final nitrate model, Study Site 2, Part B.

Figure D8-A. CART diagram for final nitrate model, Study Site 4, Part A.

Figure D9-A. CART diagram for final nitrate model, Study Site 6, Part A.

Figure D9-B. CART diagram for final nitrate model, Study Site 6, Part B.

Appendix E: Geostatistical results for As, U, and NO3-N study sites

Arsenic Study Sites

Figure E1. Study Site 1 – As IDW results.

Figure E2. Study Site 1 – As ordinary kriging results.

Figure E3. Study Site 3 – As IDW results.

Figure E4. Study Site 3 – As ordinary kriging results.

Map Credits: Source: EPA, USGS, USGS, NPS
 This map was produced as part of the CDC funded project "Development of National Screening and Site-specific Landscape Regression Models to Identify Areas with High Likelihood of Private Well Contamination" (Contract # 200-2013-37313).
 Maps produced and designed by James Vanderlicke, PhD, Marissa Tisdie, MPH, Josh Gregg, BS, Nick Faust, BS, and Adam Durrington.

Figure E5. Study Site 6 – As IDW results.

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Figure E6. Study Site 6 – As ordinary kriging results.

Uranium Study Sites

Figure E7. Study Site 3 – U IDW results.

Figure E8. Study Site 3 – U ordinary kriging results.

Figure E9. Study Site 4 – U IDW results.

Figure E10. Study Site 4 – U ordinary kriging results.

Figure E11. Study Site 5 – U IDW results.

Figure E12. Study Site 5 – U ordinary kriging results.

Nitrate Study Sites

Figure E13. Study Site 2 – NO₃-N IDW results.

Figure E14. Study Site 2 – NO₃-N ordinary kriging results.

Figure E15. Study Site 4 – NO₃-N IDW results.

Figure E16. Study Site 4 – NO₃-N ordinary kriging results.

Figure E17. Study Site – NO₃-N IDW results.

Map Credits: Source: EPA, USGS, USGS, NPS
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Figure E18. Study Site – NO₃-N ordinary kriging results.